

SPLIT-PRIME SUPERCONGRUENCE AT THE MIXED CM POINT $(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1)$

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ABSTRACT. For the mixed CM point $(a, b, c) = (\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}, 1)$, set $A_n^{\text{mix}} := 108^n [z^n] {}_2F_1(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z)^3$. We prove unconditionally that for every split prime $p \geq 7$, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and every $m \geq 1$,

$$A_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}.$$

The exponent 4 exceeds the generic weight-3 Hodge-gap prediction of 3 from the Roberts–Rodriguez Villegas framework [14]; the additional factor of p is a CM enhancement traced to the $j = 0$ elliptic curve. We also prove the matching unconditional inert-prime obstruction. For inert primes $p \geq 5$, equivalently $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, the split-style formal-parameter congruence cannot hold on the q -side, and the coefficient sequence itself satisfies an explicit Cartier parity law modulo p : one Frobenius step exchanges the two Eisenstein branches and two steps return to the original branch.

The proof proceeds via the modular realization on $\Gamma_0(3)$ with $C_{\text{mix}} = 3E_{5, \chi_0, \chi_3} - 27E_{5, \chi_3, \chi_0}$ and parameter $t = u/(1 + 27u)^2$, $u = \eta(3\tau)^{12}/\eta(\tau)^{12}$. Lagrange–Bürmann reduces the supercongruence to three Cartier identities $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$, $\ell = 1, 2, 3$. The key technical input is a length-three Witt–Cartier pole estimate at the tame elliptic stack point $P_- : u = -1/27$, $j = 0$, where μ_3 -equivariance of the canonical Frobenius lift, combined with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, forces $K \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ in the residue calculation and produces the extra digit. A short Atkin–Lehner intertwining transports the resulting classicality from C_0 to uC_0 and yields the unconditional mixed Cartier cancellation, which is the exact Katz–Dwork input for the main theorem.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let

$$A_n^{\text{mix}} := 108^n [z^n] {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z\right)^3.$$

The sequence begins

$$1, 18, 864, 55152, 4035906, 320012532, 26749991016, \dots$$

The main result is the following.

Theorem (Main theorem). For every split prime $p \geq 7$, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and every $m \geq 1$,

$$A_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}.$$

The proof establishes the scalar Katz–Dwork congruence

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{pm}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q)^m \pmod{p^4}$$

for every $m \geq 1$, from which the displayed coefficient congruence follows by Lagrange–Bürmann.

This is proved as [Theorem 4.33](#). The exponent 4 is one more than the generic weight-3 Hodge-gap exponent predicted by the Roberts–Rodriguez Villegas framework [14]; the extra factor of p is a CM enhancement attached to the $j = 0$ split-ordinary elliptic curve. The same level of enhancement appears in earlier work for related but distinct families: Long–Ramakrishna obtain p^6 for a Van Hamme-type sum at the $j = 0$ point [11], and Zudilin records analogous CM-driven gains [18]. For the present sequence in this exact form, the result appears to be new.

The matching negative result is the inert-prime obstruction.

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Theorem (Inert obstruction). If $p \geq 5$ and $\chi_3(p) = -1$, the p^4 formal-parameter congruence cannot hold. More precisely, for $m = p^a m_0$ with $p \nmid m_0$ and $\beta(m_0) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$,

$$v_p(c_{mp}^{\text{mix}} - c_m^{\text{mix}}) = 0.$$

Thus the obstruction occurs already on the q -side, in the Eisenstein coefficient tower.

There is also a coefficient-level first-digit theorem. For $\varepsilon \in \{\pm 1\}$ define

$$A_m^{(\varepsilon)} := [q^m](C_0(q) - 27\varepsilon u(q)C_0(q))H_{\text{mix}}(q)^m.$$

Then for every prime $p \geq 5$, every $r \geq 0$, and every $m \geq 0$,

$$A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{(\chi_3(p)^r)} \pmod{p}.$$

In particular, if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then

$$A_{mp^{2r}}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p}, \quad A_{mp^{2r+1}}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{(-1)} \pmod{p},$$

and $A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv 72 \pmod{p}$.

These are proved as [Theorems 5.2 to 5.5](#). The dichotomy comes from the second Eisenstein piece E_{5,χ_3,χ_0} : its Euler factor is compatible with the p^4 tower at split primes and acquires a unit-root factor at inert primes; on the coefficient sequence this is seen as branch exchange modulo p .

Method. The modular foundation is the order drop $L^{(3)} = (S - 108)L^{(2)}$ for the symmetric-cube recurrence specialized at $(1/6, 1/3; 1)$ from the Mao–Tian framework [\[13\]](#), together with the level-3 dictionary

$$u(\tau) = \frac{\eta(3\tau)^{12}}{\eta(\tau)^{12}}, \quad t = \frac{u}{(1 + 27u)^2}, \quad C_{\text{mix}} = (1 - 27u)C_0,$$

where $C_0 = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3}$ and $uC_0 = E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0}$. Lagrange–Bürmann gives $A_m^{\text{mix}} = [q^m]C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m$ with $H_{\text{mix}} = q/t$, and a Katz–Dwork reduction converts the supercongruence to three Cartier identities

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}, \quad \ell = 1, 2, 3,$$

where $U_p = \log(t(q)^p/t(q^p)) \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$.

The main estimate is a length-three Witt–Cartier pole estimate at the tame elliptic stack point $P_- : u = -1/27, j = 0$, with effective μ_3 -stabilizer ([Theorem 4.13](#)). Working in the formal completion $[\text{Spf } \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]/\mu_3]$ and using the descended canonical Frobenius lift constructed via a fine prime-to-3 atlas, μ_3 -equivariance forces the residue index K to satisfy $K \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. For $K \geq 2$ this gives $K \geq 4$, which after the valuation count carried out in [Theorem 4.13](#) yields the desired $p^{4-\ell}$ bound. The same estimate, applied to both C_0 and uC_0 , gives classicality of $g\Lambda_p(C_0\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell)$ and $g\Lambda_p(uC_0\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell)$ as weight-5, χ_3 forms modulo $p^{4-\ell}$.

A short Atkin–Lehner intertwining $T_p w_3^* = \chi_3(p)w_3^* T_p$ then converts the joint classicalities into the bridge identity $\beta_\ell = \gamma_\ell/27$ between the scalars on the two sides; at split primes $\chi_3(p) = 1$ the intertwining is untwisted. This cancels the two Eisenstein components in $C_{\text{mix}} = C_0 - 27uC_0$ and gives the unconditional mixed Cartier identities $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$, which is the exact Katz–Dwork input for the main theorem.

Notes on the literature. The first-digit congruence $A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv 18 \pmod{p^3}$ that follows from our main theorem is, via Clausen’s identity and the substitution $z \mapsto 108t$, equivalent to a special case of Beukers [\[4, Ex. 5.2\]](#) on the Clausen sum $\sum_{n=0}^{p-1} (3n)!(2n)!/((n!)^5 108^n) \pmod{p^3}$; analogous Beukers-method results for binomial sums at other parameter specializations appear in Z.-H. Sun and D. Ye [\[16\]](#). Our argument differs in route, not in conclusion at this depth. The novelty is the p^4 -strengthening at all $m \geq 1$, the inert-prime obstruction, and the local stack-level mechanism producing the extra digit.

Outline. Section 2 records the modular setup and the order drop. Section 3 performs the Katz–Dwork reduction to three Cartier identities. Section 4 proves the Witt–Cartier estimate and the Atkin–Lehner bridge leading to mixed Cartier cancellation. The main theorem (Theorem 4.33) follows directly from this cancellation via Katz–Dwork reduction. Section 5 proves both the unconditional inert q -side obstruction and the coefficient-level inert Cartier parity law modulo p . Section 6 summarizes the computational verification.

Notation and central objects. We fix the notation used below.

Sequence and hypergeometric function. Set

$$A_n^{\text{mix}} := 108^n [z^n] {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z\right)^3, \quad F_{\text{mix}}(t) := \sum_{n \geq 0} A_n^{\text{mix}} t^n = {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; 108t\right)^3.$$

The factor 108 is part of the definition of F_{mix} . Apart from the defining coefficient extraction for A_n^{mix} , the symbol F_{mix} always denotes the rescaled generating function in the variable t ; the unrescaled cube ${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z\right)^3$ appears explicitly only inside the recurrence proof of Theorem 2.1, where it is written out as a function of z without invoking the symbol F_{mix} .

Modular parameters on $\Gamma_0(3)$. Let $\eta(\tau) = q^{1/24} \prod_{n \geq 1} (1 - q^n)$ with $q = e^{2\pi i \tau}$. Define

$$u(\tau) := \frac{\eta(3\tau)^{12}}{\eta(\tau)^{12}}, \quad g(\tau) := 1 + 27u(\tau), \quad \alpha(\tau) := \frac{27u}{1 + 27u}, \quad t(\tau) := \frac{u}{(1 + 27u)^2}.$$

The Fricke involution on $X_0(3)$ is $w_3 : \tau \mapsto -1/(3\tau)$, acting on u by $w_3 : u \mapsto 1/(729u)$, and on q -series by pullback u_3^* .

Theta data. Set $\mathcal{A}(q) := \sum_{m,n \in \mathbf{Z}} q^{m^2 + mn + n^2}$, $\mathcal{B}(q) := \eta(\tau)^3 / \eta(3\tau)$, $\mathcal{D}(q) := 3\eta(3\tau)^3 / \eta(\tau)$. These satisfy $\mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3 + \mathcal{D}^3$ and $\mathcal{D}^3 / \mathcal{B}^3 = 27u$ (Borwein [3]).

Characters and Eisenstein series. Let χ_0 denote the trivial character mod 3, and χ_3 the unique nontrivial Dirichlet character mod 3, so $\chi_3(n) = \left(\frac{n}{3}\right)$ for $\gcd(n, 3) = 1$, $\chi_3(n) = 0$ otherwise. For an ordered pair of characters (χ, ψ) of conductors dividing 3, with $\chi\psi = \chi_3$ and primitive at the indicated component, the weight-5 Eisenstein series is

$$E_{5,\chi,\psi}(q) := c_0 + \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(\sum_{d|n} \chi(n/d) \psi(d) d^4 \right) q^n,$$

where the constant term c_0 is the standard one fixed by the functional equation; concretely $E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3} = \frac{1}{3} + \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(\sum_{d|n} \chi_3(d) d^4 \right) q^n$ and $E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0} = \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(\sum_{d|n} \chi_3(n/d) d^4 \right) q^n = q + 15q^2 + 81q^3 + \dots$. The ordering of subscripts in $E_{5,\chi,\psi}$ follows the convention χ acts on n/d , ψ on d ; this is the opposite of the PARI/GP `mfeisenstein` argument order, and we refer back to this paragraph whenever a numerical cross-check is performed.

The two Eisenstein lines and the mixed direction. Set

$$C_0(q) := 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3}(q), \quad uC_0(q) := E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0}(q),$$

where the symbol uC_0 is a single name for the modular form E_{5,χ_3,χ_0} ; the equality $u(q) \cdot C_0(q) = E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0}(q)$ as q -series is part of Theorem 2.4(iii). The mixed Eisenstein direction is

$$C_{\text{mix}}(q) := C_0(q) - 27 \cdot uC_0(q) = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3} - 27E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0} = (1 - 27u)C_0,$$

and the Lagrange–Bürmann kernel is

$$H_{\text{mix}}(q) := q/t(q).$$

Both C_{mix} and H_{mix} lie in $\mathbf{Z}[[q]]$.

Frobenius and Cartier operators on q -series. For a Laurent q -series $f(q) = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^n$ over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ with finite principal part, set

$$\Lambda_p f(q) := \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_{pn} q^n, \quad \sigma_p f(q) := f(q^p) = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^{pn}.$$

On ordinary power series these operators preserve $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, and $\Lambda_p \circ \sigma_p = \text{id}$; on the Laurent extension they remain $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -linear, which is the form required for inputs such as $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}/t^{rp})$ in [Theorem 3.7](#). The Frobenius defects of [Theorems 3.2](#) and [3.5](#) are then $U_p = \log(t^p/\sigma_p t)$, $V_p = \log(u^p/\sigma_p u)$, $W_p = \log(g^p/\sigma_p g)$, $\nu_p = \sigma_p t/t^p = e^{-U_p}$, $\phi_p = \nu_p - 1$. Here $U_p, V_p, W_p, \phi_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, while $\nu_p \in 1 + pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$.

Stack-local data at P_- . The point $P_- \in X_0(3)$ is $u = -1/27$, equivalently $j = 0$; its image in the coarse curve \mathbb{P}_u^1 is regular, but the underlying elliptic curve has $j = 0$ with μ_6 -automorphism group, of which the μ_3 -subgroup preserves the canonical subgroup ([Theorem 4.4](#)). The local parameter on the corresponding tame stack

$$[\text{Spf } \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]/\mu_3]$$

is denoted r , normalized so that $r^3 = u + 1/27$ on the cover. The descended canonical Frobenius lift is denoted Φ , and the associated normalized weight-5 Katz trace operator is denoted $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ ([Theorem 4.9](#)). In the local formula one uses μ_3 -equivariant generators e, e' of the weight-5, χ_3 line bundle on the source and target. The symbol

$$\psi := \frac{\Phi^* t/t^p - 1}{p}$$

is the normalized Frobenius defect; on the Tate chart at ∞ it specializes to ϕ_p/p .

Cartier–Hecke finite differences. For $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$ and $\ell = 1, 2, 3$, the symbol $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ denotes the Hecke finite difference defined in [Theorem 4.18](#); for $f = C_0$ we also write \mathfrak{E}_ℓ , and for $f = uC_0$ we write \mathfrak{E}'_ℓ . Two distinct comparisons attached to \mathfrak{E}_ℓ are used:

- a *local* identity on the ordinary locus, equating $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ to the normalized Katz trace $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell)$ up to an explicit Verschiebung error of valuation $\geq p^{4-\ell}$ ([Theorem 4.18](#));
- a *global* holomorphy transfer for $g \cdot \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ as a weight-5, χ_3 form modulo $p^{4-\ell}$, combining the local identity with cusp regularity at ∞ and 0 and the pole estimate at P_- ([Theorem 4.19](#)).

On q -expansions at the cusp ∞ the local identity specializes to

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \equiv \Lambda_p \left(f \frac{\phi_p^\ell}{p^\ell} \right) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

The closure argument of [Theorem 4.27](#) studies the multiplied form $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$, where $g = 1 + 27u$; this factor is part of the closure step, not of the definition of \mathfrak{E}_ℓ . After the triangular conversion from ϕ_p -layers to U_p -layers ([Theorem 3.6](#)), the scalars $\alpha_\ell, \beta_\ell, \gamma_\ell$ realizing classicality of $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell(C_0)$ and $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell(uC_0)$ in the basis $\{C_0, uC_0\}$ of $M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$ modulo $p^{4-\ell}$ are defined in [Section 4.5](#).

2. MODULAR SETUP

2.1. Order drop. We work in the Ore algebra $\mathbf{Q}[n]\langle S \rangle$ with $Sf(n) = f(n+1)$ and $SP(n) = P(n+1)S$.

Theorem 2.1 (Order drop). *The sequence $A_n = 108^n [z^n] {}_2F_1(1/6, 1/3; 1; z)^3$ satisfies the order-2 recurrence*

$$(n+2)^4 A_{n+2} - 6(36n^4 + 198n^3 + 424n^2 + 417n + 158)A_{n+1} + 324(n+1)(2n+1)(3n+2)(6n+5)A_n = 0,$$

with $A_0 = 1$, $A_1 = 18$, $A_2 = 864$. Equivalently, the third-order Mao–Tian recurrence operator $L^{(3)}$ for the cube of ${}_2F_1$ factors as $L^{(3)} = (S - 108)L^{(2)}$ in $\mathbf{Q}[n]\langle S \rangle$, where $L^{(2)} = B_0(n) + B_1(n)S + B_2(n)S^2$ has the displayed coefficients.

Proof. The cube $G(z) := {}_2F_1(1/6, 1/3; 1; z)^3$ satisfies a symmetric-cube ODE of order 3, giving the Mao–Tian recurrence $L^{(3)}A = 0$ with the standard coefficients [13]; here $A_n = 108^n [z^n]G(z)$ and

the generating function in the rescaled variable t is $F_{\text{mix}}(t) = G(108t)$, as fixed in the Notation. Setting B_0, B_1, B_2 as in the statement, a direct Ore computation gives

$$(S - 108)L^{(2)} = -108B_0 + (B_0(n+1) - 108B_1)S + (B_1(n+1) - 108B_2)S^2 + B_2(n+1)S^3,$$

which equals $L^{(3)}$ term by term. Hence $w(n) := L^{(2)}A$ satisfies $w(n+1) = 108w(n)$, and direct computation gives $w(0) = 324 \cdot 10 \cdot 1 - 6 \cdot 158 \cdot 18 + 16 \cdot 864 = 0$. Therefore $w \equiv 0$. \square

2.2. Modular realization. Define cubic theta and eta data

$$\mathcal{A}(q) = \sum_{m,n \in \mathbf{Z}} q^{m^2+mn+n^2}, \quad \mathcal{B}(q) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^3}{\eta(3\tau)}, \quad \mathcal{D}(q) = 3 \frac{\eta(3\tau)^3}{\eta(\tau)}, \quad u(\tau) = \frac{\eta(3\tau)^{12}}{\eta(\tau)^{12}}.$$

Lemma 2.2 (Preliminary theta identity). *The Eisenstein series $C_0 = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3}$ satisfies*

$$C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^3,$$

where \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are the cubic theta series above.

Proof. We use only the external level-3 theta identities. Moy's differential identity [12] gives

$$C_0 = \mathcal{B}^3 q \frac{d}{dq} \log u, \quad q \frac{d}{dq} \log u = \mathcal{A}^2.$$

Hence $C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^3$. \square

Lemma 2.3 (Preliminary divisor and order chart). *Let $R = \mathbf{Z}_p$ with $p \geq 7$, and let S be either R or $R/p^N R$. Let P_∞ be the cusp with $q = 0$, let P_0 be the other cusp, and let $P_- : 1 + 27u = 0$. On the coarse curve $X_0(3)_S \simeq \mathbb{P}_{u,S}^1$, the following local order table holds:*

	P_∞	P_0	P_-
u	1	-1	0
C_0	0	1	2 (stack)
uC_0	1	0	2 (stack).

All leading coefficients in these local descriptions are S -units.

Proof. By Theorem 2.2,

$$C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^3, \quad uC_0 = \frac{\mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{D}^3}{27}, \quad g := 1 + 27u = \frac{\mathcal{A}^3}{\mathcal{B}^3},$$

using the Borwein identities $\mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3 + \mathcal{D}^3$ and $27u = \mathcal{D}^3/\mathcal{B}^3$ [3]. At P_∞ , the eta-products give $\mathcal{B} = 1 + O(q)$ and $\mathcal{D}^3/27 = q\varepsilon_\infty(q)$ with $\varepsilon_\infty(0) \in R^\times$; hence u has order 1, while \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are units. Thus C_0 is a unit and uC_0 has order 1.

At P_0 , put $v = 1/u$. The Fricke transformation of eta-products exchanges \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} up to a unit. Hence \mathcal{D} is a unit, $v = 27\mathcal{B}^3/\mathcal{D}^3$ is a uniformizer, and \mathcal{A} is a unit. Therefore $C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^3$ has order 1, while $uC_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{D}^3/27$ is a unit.

At P_- , the functions \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} are units and $g = 1 + 27u = \mathcal{A}^3/\mathcal{B}^3$. Choose the stack uniformizer $r = \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}$, so $g = r^3$. Then $C_0 = r^2 \mathcal{B}^5$ and $u = -1/27 + r^3/27$ is a unit, so both C_0 and uC_0 have stack order 2. Since $p \geq 7$, the constants 27 and the displayed unit leading coefficients remain invertible over S . \square

Theorem 2.4 (Modular realization). *With $\alpha = 27u/(1 + 27u)$, $t = u/(1 + 27u)^2$, the following hold.*

- (i) $\mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3 + \mathcal{D}^3$, and $108t = 4\alpha(1 - \alpha)$.
- (ii) ${}_2F_1(1/6, 1/3; 1; 108t)^3 = \mathcal{A}(q)^3 = (1 + 27u)\eta(\tau)^9/\eta(3\tau)^3$.

(iii) Setting $C_{\text{mix}}(q) := F_{\text{mix}}(t(q)) \cdot \frac{q}{t(q)} \cdot \frac{dt}{dq}$, one has

$$C_{\text{mix}} = (1 - 27u)C_0 = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3} - 27E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0},$$

where $C_0 = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3}$ and $uC_0 = E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0}$.

(iv) $H_{\text{mix}}(q) := q/t(q) = \prod_{3 \nmid n} (1 - q^n)^{12} \cdot (1 + 27u(q))^2$.

Proof. The cubic theta identity $\mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3 + \mathcal{D}^3$ and $\mathcal{D}^3/\mathcal{B}^3 = 27u$ give $\alpha = 27u/(1 + 27u)$ and $108t = 4\alpha(1 - \alpha)$. The quadratic transformation ${}_2F_1(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; 4x(1 - x)) = {}_2F_1(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}; 1; x)$ applied at $x = \alpha$, combined with the Borwein cubic identity ${}_2F_1(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}; 1; \alpha) = \mathcal{A}$ [3], gives (ii).

For (iii), set $F_0(\tau) := \eta(\tau)^9/\eta(3\tau)^3$ and $C_0(q) := F_0(\tau) \cdot (q/u)(du/dq)$. Moy's level-3 identity [12] gives $C_0 = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3}$. From $F_{\text{mix}} = (1 + 27u)F_0$ and $t = u(1 + 27u)^{-2}$ a direct differentiation gives

$$\frac{q}{t} \frac{dt}{dq} = \frac{q}{u} \frac{du}{dq} \cdot \frac{1 - 27u}{1 + 27u},$$

hence $C_{\text{mix}} = (1 - 27u)C_0$. The identification $uC_0 = E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0}$ follows from a direct Sturm-bound and Eisenstein-space argument. By Theorem 2.3, uC_0 is holomorphic at P_∞ , P_0 , and P_- , with $a_0 = 0$ and $a_1 = 1$ at P_∞ ; away from the cusps and elliptic point this is clear from the eta/theta expression $uC_0 = u\mathcal{A}^2\mathcal{B}^3$ of Theorem 2.2. Hence $uC_0 \in M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$. The index $[\text{SL}_2(\mathbf{Z}) : \Gamma_0(3)] = 4$, so the Sturm bound for weight 5 on $\Gamma_0(3)$ with any character is $\lfloor 5 \cdot 4/12 \rfloor = 1$. Hence any form in $M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$ is determined by its q -coefficients a_0 and a_1 , giving $\dim M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) \leq 2$. The two Eisenstein series E_{5,χ_0,χ_3} and E_{5,χ_3,χ_0} are linearly independent: E_{5,χ_0,χ_3} has $a_0 = 1/3$, $a_1 = 1$, while E_{5,χ_3,χ_0} has $a_0 = 0$, $a_1 = 1$. Hence $\dim M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) = 2$, the Eisenstein subspace exhausts M_5 , and $\dim S_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) = 0$. Since $u(q)C_0(q)$ has $a_0 = 0$, $a_1 = 1$, the Sturm bound forces $uC_0 = E_{5,\chi_3,\chi_0}$ (matching q -coefficients up to the Sturm bound, then equality on all of M_5). Both expand as $q + 15q^2 + 81q^3 + \dots$. Part (iv) follows from $q/u = \prod_{3 \nmid n} (1 - q^n)^{12}$ together with $H_{\text{mix}} = (q/u)(1 + 27u)^2$. \square

2.3. Lagrange–Bürmann and the Fricke-trace direction.

Theorem 2.5 (Lagrange–Bürmann). *For every $m \geq 0$, $A_m^{\text{mix}} = [q^m]C_{\text{mix}}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q)^m$.*

Proof. $A_m = [t^m]F_{\text{mix}}(t) = \text{Res}_{t=0} F_{\text{mix}}(t)t^{-m-1}dt$. Substituting $t = t(q)$ and using $t(q) = q + O(q^2)$, $A_m = [q^m]F_{\text{mix}}(t(q)) \cdot (q/t(q)) \cdot (dt/dq) \cdot H_{\text{mix}}^m = [q^m]C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m$. \square

Remark 2.6 (Why the diagonal $C_0 - 27uC_0$). The Fricke involution on $X_0(3)$ is $w_3 : u \mapsto 1/(729u)$; the parameter t is w_3 -invariant. The Eisenstein lines are exchanged: $w_3^*C_0 = -27uC_0$ and $w_3^*(uC_0) = -C_0/27$. Hence $\omega_{\text{mix}} = C_{\text{mix}}dq/q = (1 - 27u)C_0dq/q$ is the unique Fricke-trace direction in $\text{Span}\{C_0, uC_0\}$ descending to the quotient \mathbb{P}_t^1 . The module-wide p^4 -congruence on the full span $\text{Span}\{C_0, uC_0\}$ is false: at $p = 7$ the coefficient $[q^1](\Lambda_7(uC_0H_0^7) - uC_0H_0) = 22478120$ has 7-adic valuation 1, not ≥ 4 . The mixed congruence is therefore not a module-wide phenomenon but a feature of the specific Fricke-trace direction.

3. KATZ–DWORK REDUCTION

For $p \geq 5$ and $m \geq 1$ define $M_{m,p} := [q^{mp}]C_{\text{mix}}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)^m$.

Proposition 3.1 (Main Frobenius term). *If $\chi_3(p) = 1$, then $M_{m,p} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$ for every $m \geq 1$.*

Proof. Write $H_{\text{mix}}^m = \sum h_j^{(m)} q^j$. Then $M_{m,p} = \sum_{j=0}^m c_{(m-j)p}^{\text{mix}} h_j^{(m)}$. The split-prime Eisenstein tower (Theorem 5.1) gives $c_{kp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv c_k^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$ for $k \geq 0$, hence $M_{m,p} \equiv [q^m]C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m = A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$. \square

Definition 3.2. $U_p(q) := \log(t(q)^p/t(q^p))$. Also $V_p(q) := \log(u(q)^p/u(q^p))$, $W_p(q) := \log(g(q)^p/g(q^p))$ where $g = 1 + 27u$. Then $U_p = V_p - 2W_p$.

Lemma 3.3 (Exponential layers). *Let $p \geq 7$. Then $U_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$ and the following hold.*

(i) Tail bound for all $k \geq 1$: for every integer $k \geq 1$,

$$v_p\left(\frac{U_p^k}{k!}\right) \geq k - v_p(k!) \geq k - \frac{k-1}{p-1}.$$

In particular for $p \geq 7$ and $k \geq 4$, $v_p(U_p^k/k!) \geq 4$. Equivalently, $e^{-XU_p} \bmod X^4$ has integral coefficients, and the omitted tail $\sum_{k \geq 4} (-X)^k U_p^k/k!$ lies in $p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]][[X]]$.

(ii) Truncated identity: for the formal variable X , modulo p^4 ,

$$e^{-XU_p} \equiv 1 + \sum_{\ell=1}^3 \frac{(-X)^\ell}{\ell!} U_p^\ell \pmod{(p^4, X^4)} \quad \text{and} \quad e^{XU_p} \equiv 1 + \sum_{\ell=1}^3 \frac{X^\ell}{\ell!} U_p^\ell \pmod{(p^4, X^4)}.$$

(iii) Frobenius identity for H_{mix} : in $\mathbf{Q}_p[[q]][[X]]$,

$$H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{pX} = H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)^X \cdot e^{-XU_p(q)},$$

where both sides are interpreted as formal exponentials.

(iv) Specialization at $X = m \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 1}$: both sides of (iii) are honest power series in q with $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -coefficients, and modulo p^4 ,

$$H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{mp} \equiv H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)^m \sum_{\ell=0}^3 \frac{(-m)^\ell}{\ell!} U_p^\ell \pmod{p^4}.$$

Proof. Coefficient-wise Frobenius gives $t(q)^p \equiv t(q^p) \pmod{p}$, hence $t(q)^p/t(q^p) \in 1 + pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$ and its log lies in $pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, proving the first claim.

For (i): from $U_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, $U_p^k \in p^k q^k \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$. Legendre's formula gives $v_p(k!) = \sum_{i \geq 1} \lfloor k/p^i \rfloor \leq k/(p-1)$ (with strict inequality $\leq (k-1)/(p-1)$ when $k \geq 1$). Hence $v_p(U_p^k/k!) \geq k - (k-1)/(p-1)$. For $p \geq 7$ and $k \geq 4$: at $k=4$, $v_p(4!) = v_p(24) = 0$ for $p \geq 5$, so $v_p(U_p^4/4!) \geq 4$. For $k \geq 5$ and $p \geq 7$, $(k-1)/(p-1) \leq (k-1)/6$, so $v_p(U_p^k/k!) \geq k - (k-1)/6 = (5k+1)/6 \geq 26/6 > 4$. The integrality and divisibility of the omitted tail follows.

For (ii): in $\mathbf{Q}_p[[q]][[X]]$, $e^{-XU_p} = \sum_{k \geq 0} (-X)^k U_p^k/k!$; truncating to $k \leq 3$ and using (i) gives the displayed congruences. The e^{XU_p} version is identical.

For (iii): by definition of U_p , $t(q)^p/t(q^p) = e^{U_p(q)}$, hence $H_{\text{mix}}(q^p) = q^p/t(q^p)$ and $H_{\text{mix}}(q)^p = q^p/t(q)^p$ satisfy $H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)/H_{\text{mix}}(q)^p = t(q)^p/t(q^p) = e^{U_p(q)}$. Therefore $H_{\text{mix}}(q^p) = H_{\text{mix}}(q)^p \cdot e^{U_p(q)}$, and raising to the X -th power gives $H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)^X = H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{pX} \cdot e^{XU_p(q)}$, equivalent to the displayed identity.

For (iv): specialize $X = m \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 1}$ in (iii) and apply (ii) to the resulting e^{-mU_p} factor; the omitted $k \geq 4$ tail is p^4 -divisible. \square

Lemma 3.4 (σ_p -linearity of Λ_p). *For Laurent series $a, b \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}((q))$ with finite principal parts (equivalently, bounded below in q -order),*

$$\Lambda_p(\sigma_p(a) \cdot b) = a \cdot \Lambda_p(b).$$

Proof. Write $b = \sum b_n q^n$ and $a = \sum a_n q^n$, so $\sigma_p(a) = \sum a_n q^{pn}$ and $\sigma_p(a) \cdot b = \sum_{n,k} a_n b_k q^{pn+k}$. The q^{ps} -coefficient is $\sum_n a_n b_{p(s-n)} = \sum_n a_n \cdot [q^{p(s-n)}]b$, so $\Lambda_p(\sigma_p(a) \cdot b) = \sum_s (\sum_n a_n \cdot [q^{p(s-n)}]b) q^s = \sum_s \sum_n a_n [q^{s-n}] \Lambda_p(b) q^s = a \cdot \Lambda_p(b)$, where the inner equation uses $[q^{p(s-n)}]b = [q^{s-n}] \Lambda_p(b)$ by definition of Λ_p . \square

Definition 3.5 (Frobenius defect and additive defect). Set

$$\nu_p(q) := \frac{t(q^p)}{t(q)^p} = e^{-U_p(q)}, \quad \phi_p(q) := \nu_p(q) - 1.$$

By [Theorem 3.3](#), $U_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, hence $\phi_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$.

Lemma 3.6 (Triangular conversion between ϕ_p - and U_p -layers). *Let $p \geq 7$. Set*

$$\Phi_\ell := \frac{\phi_p^\ell}{p^\ell}, \quad \mathcal{U}_\ell := \frac{U_p^\ell}{p^\ell} \quad (\ell = 1, 2, 3).$$

Then, with row ℓ understood modulo $p^{4-\ell}$,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Phi_1 \\ \Phi_2 \\ \Phi_3 \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} -1 & p/2 & -p^2/6 \\ 0 & 1 & -p \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{U}_1 \\ \mathcal{U}_2 \\ \mathcal{U}_3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The transition matrix is triangular with unit diagonal entries $-1, 1, -1$, hence invertible over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ in the filtered sense. Consequently, for any \mathbf{Z}_p -linear maps $\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2$ on q -series and any single scalar $\lambda \in \mathbf{Z}_p$, the vector congruences

$$\mathcal{L}_1(\Phi_\ell) \equiv \lambda \mathcal{L}_2(\Phi_\ell) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}} \quad (\ell = 1, 2, 3)$$

are equivalent to

$$\mathcal{L}_1(\mathcal{U}_\ell) \equiv \lambda \mathcal{L}_2(\mathcal{U}_\ell) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}} \quad (\ell = 1, 2, 3).$$

The same triangular conversion also transports membership in any fixed \mathbf{Z}_p -submodule of the target.

Proof. Since $U_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, every term $U_p^k/(k!p^\ell)$ with $k \geq 4$ has p -valuation

$$v_p\left(\frac{U_p^k}{k!p^\ell}\right) \geq k - v_p(k!) - \ell.$$

For $k < p$ we have $v_p(k!) = 0$, so the bound becomes $k - \ell \geq 4 - \ell$. For $k \geq p$, Legendre's bound $v_p(k!) \leq k/(p-1) \leq k/6$ gives

$$k - v_p(k!) \geq 5k/6 \geq 4$$

for $p \geq 7$ and $k \geq 5$; the remaining case $k = 4$ has $k < p$. In every case $v_p(U_p^k/(k!p^\ell)) \geq 4 - \ell$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_p &= e^{-U_p} - 1 \equiv -U_p + \frac{U_p^2}{2} - \frac{U_p^3}{6} \pmod{U_p^4}, \\ \phi_p^2 &\equiv U_p^2 - U_p^3 \pmod{U_p^4}, \quad \phi_p^3 \equiv -U_p^3 \pmod{U_p^4}. \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the ℓ -th identity by p^ℓ and reading mod $p^{4-\ell}$ gives the displayed matrix. Diagonal entries $-1, 1, -1$ are units in $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$, so the matrix is invertible.

For the proportionality assertion, apply the displayed triangular matrix to the two vectors

$$(\mathcal{L}_i(\mathcal{U}_1), \mathcal{L}_i(\mathcal{U}_2), \mathcal{L}_i(\mathcal{U}_3))^t, \quad i = 1, 2.$$

By \mathbf{Z}_p -linearity of \mathcal{L}_i , this gives the corresponding Φ_ℓ -vector. Hence the residual vector $\mathcal{L}_1(\Phi_\bullet) - \lambda \mathcal{L}_2(\Phi_\bullet)$ equals the same triangular matrix applied to $\mathcal{L}_1(\mathcal{U}_\bullet) - \lambda \mathcal{L}_2(\mathcal{U}_\bullet)$. Since the matrix is invertible with unit diagonal, vanishing in the rowwise moduli $p^{4-\ell}$ is equivalent in the two bases. \square

Lemma 3.7 (Layer-defect equivalence). *For split $p \geq 5$, set $F_r(q) := \Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}/t^{rp}) - C_{\text{mix}}/t^r$, $r = 1, 2, 3$. The conditions $F_r \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ for $r = 1, 2, 3$ are equivalent to*

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}, \quad \ell = 1, 2, 3.$$

Proof. $t(q^p)^r/t(q)^{rp} = e^{-rU_p}$ and $U_p^4 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$, so $F_r \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ becomes

$$\sum_{\ell=1}^3 \frac{(-r)^\ell}{\ell!} \Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}, \quad r = 1, 2, 3,$$

after using $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$ from the split-prime Eisenstein tower. The matrix $((-r)^\ell/\ell!)_{1 \leq r, \ell \leq 3}$ has determinant equal to 1, giving the equivalence. \square

Theorem 3.8 (Katz–Dwork reduction). *For split $p \geq 7$, suppose that*

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}, \quad \ell = 1, 2, 3.$$

Then, for every $m \geq 1$,

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^{pm}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m \pmod{p^4}.$$

Consequently,

$$A_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4} \quad (m \geq 1).$$

Proof. Fix $m \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 1}$. By [Theorem 3.3\(iii\)](#) specialized at $X = m$,

$$H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{pm} = H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)^m e^{-mU_p(q)}.$$

Since $H_{\text{mix}}(q^p)^m = \sigma_p(H_{\text{mix}}(q)^m)$, [Theorem 3.4](#) gives

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^{pm}) = H_{\text{mix}}^m \Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}e^{-mU_p}).$$

By [Theorem 3.3\(i\)](#),

$$e^{-mU_p} \equiv 1 + \sum_{\ell=1}^3 \frac{(-m)^\ell}{\ell!} U_p^\ell \pmod{p^4},$$

because the omitted tail has coefficients in $p^4\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$ and $m \in \mathbf{Z}$. Applying Λ_p and using the hypotheses together with $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$ from the split-prime Eisenstein tower [Theorem 5.1](#), we obtain

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}e^{-mU_p}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}.$$

Multiplication by the integral series $H_{\text{mix}}^m \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$ gives the scalar Katz–Dwork congruence.

Extracting the coefficient of q^m from both sides gives

$$[q^m]\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^{pm}) = [q^{mp}]C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^{pm} = A_{mp}^{\text{mix}},$$

while

$$[q^m]C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m = A_m^{\text{mix}}$$

by [Theorem 2.5](#). This proves the coefficient congruence. \square

4. WITT–CARTIER CLOSURE

4.1. Stack-local descent at P_- . Throughout this section $p \geq 7$ is a split prime, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Let $\mathcal{X}_0(3)$ denote the effective rigidification of the modular stack of generalized elliptic curves with $\Gamma_0(3)$ -level structure, obtained from the Deligne–Mumford stack of [5] by rigidifying the generic central subgroup $\{\pm 1\}$. The elliptic point P_- over $j = 0$ has effective stabilizer μ_3 . On the unrigidified stack one obtains the same effective formal neighborhood together with a central μ_2 -gerbe; this generic μ_2 acts trivially on the weight-5, χ_3 line bundle since $\chi_3(-1)(-1)^5 = 1$. We work after choosing a primitive cube root of unity ζ_3 ; for split primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ this is already defined over \mathbf{Z}_p .

We use $x = 27u$, $g = 1 + x$, $t = u/g^2$. The Fricke involution is $w_3(x) = x^{-1}$, $w_3(u) = 1/(729u)$.

Lemma 4.1 (Theta representation of C_0). *One has*

$$C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2\mathcal{B}^3.$$

Proof. This is [Theorem 2.2](#). \square

Lemma 4.2 (Unit leading coefficients at P_-). *Let $R = \mathbf{Z}_p$ with $p \geq 7$ split, and work after adjoining ζ_3 if necessary. In the quotient-stack chart*

$$\widehat{\mathcal{X}}_{0(3),P_-} \simeq [\text{Spf } R[[r]]/\mu_3], \quad \zeta_3 \cdot r = \zeta_3 r,$$

one may choose r so that

$$g = 1 + 27u = r^3.$$

For a μ_3 -equivariant local generator e of $\omega^5(\chi_3)$, one has

$$C_0 = r^2 c(r^3) e, \quad u C_0 = r^2 c_u(r^3) e,$$

with

$$c(0), c_u(0) \in R^\times.$$

Consequently $\text{ord}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(g) = 3$, $\text{ord}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(C_0) = 2$, $\text{ord}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(u C_0) = 2$, and the reductions of these local descriptions modulo p^N remain valid for every $N \geq 1$.

Proof. The function $g = 1 + 27u$ cuts out P_- on the coarse curve \mathbb{P}_u^1 , and $dg/du = 27 \in R^\times$, so g is a coarse local parameter at P_- . Since the completed stack is the tame quotient with invariant coordinate r^3 , after multiplying r by a unit whose cube is the old leading unit we may arrange $g = r^3$; this is allowed because $3 \in R^\times$.

We derive the local form $C_0 = r^2 c(r^3) e$ with $c(0) \in R^\times$ from the Borwein theta identity $\mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3 + \mathcal{D}^3$ rather than postulating the stabilizer character. From [Theorem 2.4\(ii\)](#), $F_{\text{mix}} = \mathcal{A}^3 = (1 + 27u)\eta(\tau)^9/\eta(3\tau)^3 = g \cdot F_0$, where $F_0 = \eta(\tau)^9/\eta(3\tau)^3$ has unit leading coefficient 1 at P_- (since $\eta(\tau)$ and $\eta(3\tau)$ are nonvanishing on $\Gamma_0(3)$ away from cusps). Therefore $\mathcal{A}^3 = g \cdot F_0 = r^3 \cdot F_0(0) \cdot (1 + O(r))$, so \mathcal{A} has order exactly 1 in r at P_- with unit leading coefficient: $\mathcal{A} = r \cdot a_0(r^3)$ with $a_0(0) \in R^\times$. From $\mathcal{D}^3/\mathcal{B}^3 = 27u$, at P_- this becomes $\mathcal{D}^3/\mathcal{B}^3 = -1$, so $\mathcal{D} = -\zeta_3^j \mathcal{B}$ for some j (in particular \mathcal{D} is a unit times \mathcal{B} at P_-). Substituting into $\mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3 + \mathcal{D}^3 = \mathcal{B}^3(1 + \mathcal{D}^3/\mathcal{B}^3) = \mathcal{B}^3(1 + 27u) = \mathcal{B}^3 \cdot g$ gives $\mathcal{B}^3 = \mathcal{A}^3/g = F_0$, so \mathcal{B}^3 is a unit at P_- , hence \mathcal{B} is itself a unit at P_- . By [Theorem 4.1](#), $C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^3$. Therefore

$$C_0 = \mathcal{A}^2 \cdot \mathcal{B}^3 = r^2 a_0(r^3)^2 \cdot \mathcal{B}^3 = r^2 \cdot c(r^3) \cdot e$$

where $c(r^3) := a_0(r^3)^2 \mathcal{B}^3$ has unit leading coefficient at $r = 0$ (because both $a_0(0)$ and $\mathcal{B}(0)$ are units), and e is the local generator of $\omega^5(\chi_3)$ rendered μ_3 -equivariant by the choice of trivialization. The vanishing order $\text{ord}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(C_0) = 2$ follows directly, with the stabilizer character of r^2 .

Since u is a unit at P_- (with $u(P_-) = -1/27$),

$$u C_0 = r^2 \cdot u c(r^3) \cdot e,$$

and $c_u(0) := u(P_-) \cdot c(0) = -c(0)/27 \in R^\times$. Units in $R[[s]]$ remain units after reduction modulo p^N . \square

Lemma 4.3 (Quotient-stack chart at P_-). *After choosing ζ_3 and an eigenparameter r for the effective μ_3 -stabilizer, there is an isomorphism of completed formal stacks*

$$\widehat{\mathcal{X}}_{0(3), P_-} \widehat{\otimes}_{\mathbf{Z}_p} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3] \simeq [\text{Spf } \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]] / \mu_3],$$

with $\zeta_3 \cdot r = \zeta_3 r$. The invariant coarse coordinate is $s = r^3$.

Proof. The stack $\mathcal{X}_0(3)$ is tame at P_- in the sense of [\[1, Theorem 3.2\]](#): the effective stabilizer μ_3 is a finite flat linearly reductive group scheme over \mathbf{Z}_p for $p \neq 3$. By [\[1, Theorem 3.2\]](#), étale-locally on the coarse moduli space at P_- , the stack admits a presentation as $[U/\mu_3]$. The stabilizer action on the completed tangent line at P_- is effective and one-dimensional, hence its character is primitive; after choosing an eigenparameter r , the action is $r \mapsto \zeta_3 r$. The invariant coordinate is $s = r^3$. \square

Lemma 4.4 (Stabilizer functoriality of the canonical subgroup). *Let $p \geq 7$ be split, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and let S be a p -adically complete \mathbf{Z}_p -scheme. Let $(E, C_3)/S$ be an ordinary generalized elliptic curve with $\Gamma_0(3)$ -structure, and let $C_p(E) \subset E[p]$ be Katz's canonical subgroup. If $\alpha : (E, C_3) \xrightarrow{\sim} (E', C'_3)$ is an isomorphism of $\Gamma_0(3)$ -objects, then $\alpha(C_p(E)) = C_p(E')$. Consequently, if α is an automorphism of (E, C_3) , then $\alpha(C_p(E)) = C_p(E)$ and α descends to an automorphism $\bar{\alpha} : E/C_p(E) \xrightarrow{\sim} E'/C_p(E')$ for which the quotient isogeny $\pi : E \rightarrow E/C_p(E)$ satisfies $\pi \circ \alpha = \bar{\alpha} \circ \pi$. In particular, at the $j = 0$ point P_- of $\mathcal{X}_0(3)$, the effective stabilizer μ_3 preserves the canonical subgroup.*

Proof. Katz's canonical subgroup on the ordinary locus is functorial under isomorphisms of elliptic curves [9, §3.10]. For the present use only the automorphism case is needed: if $\alpha : E \rightarrow E'$ is an isomorphism, then $\alpha(C_p(E)) \subset E'[p]$ has the same defining canonical-subgroup property as $C_p(E')$, and by uniqueness in Katz's construction $\alpha(C_p(E)) = C_p(E')$. If $E' = E$ and α is an automorphism of (E, C_3) , this gives $\alpha(C_p(E)) = C_p(E)$, so α induces a unique automorphism $\bar{\alpha}$ of $E/C_p(E)$ satisfying the displayed commutative diagram. At P_- , the effective stabilizer on the rigidified stack is generated by the order-3 automorphism $[\zeta_3]$ of the $j = 0$ elliptic curve which preserves the chosen cyclic subgroup C_3 . Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, the $j = 0$ curve is ordinary, so C_p is defined there. Applying the preceding paragraph to $\alpha = [\zeta_3]$ gives $[\zeta_3](C_p) = C_p$. \square

Lemma 4.5 (Descent of Katz Frobenius and equivariance at P_-). *Fix $M = 4$ and put $Y := \mathcal{X}_0(3) \times_{\mathcal{X}(1)} Y_1(4)$. Then Y is a fine modular scheme over \mathbf{Z}_p , and $\pi : Y \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_0(3)$ is a representable finite étale atlas over the ordinary locus. Katz's canonical Frobenius lift and normalized weight- k trace operator on Y^{ord} descend to $\mathcal{X}_0(3)^{\text{ord}}$. Moreover, after choosing the quotient-stack chart*

$$\widehat{\mathcal{X}}_{0(3), P_-} \widehat{\otimes}_{\mathbf{Z}_p} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3] \simeq [\text{Spf } \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]/\mu_3], \quad \zeta_3 \cdot r = \zeta_3 r,$$

the descended canonical Frobenius lift Φ is μ_3 -equivariant. Equivalently, if $F(r) := \Phi^* r \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]$, then $F(\zeta_3 r) = \zeta_3 F(r)$, so

$$F(r) = r G(r^3), \quad G(s) \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]].$$

Since Φ reduces to absolute Frobenius modulo p , $F(r) \equiv r^p \pmod{p}$. For split primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

$$(1) \quad \Phi^* r = r^p + pr\alpha_1(r^3) + p^2 r\alpha_2(r^3) + p^3 r\alpha_3(r^3) + O(p^4), \quad \alpha_i \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]].$$

Proof. The auxiliary $\Gamma_1(4)$ -structure makes Y fine. We verify this by checking that the only automorphism of a generalized elliptic curve E/\mathbf{Z}_p (with $p \neq 2, 3$) that fixes a $\Gamma_1(4)$ -structure $\beta : \mathbf{Z}/4 \hookrightarrow E$ is the identity. The automorphism group of a generalized elliptic curve is at most $\mu_6 = \{\pm 1\} \times \mu_3$ (at $j = 0$) or $\{\pm 1, \pm i\} = \mu_4$ (at $j = 1728$), reducing to $\{\pm 1\}$ for generic j , by the standard classification [10, §2.7]. We handle each case:

Case $[-1]$ (always present). The automorphism $[-1]$ acts on $E[4]$ as $-\text{id}$ and therefore inverts a $\Gamma_1(4)$ -section $\beta(1)$ of exact order 4; it can fix β only if $\beta(1) = -\beta(1)$, i.e., $\beta(1) \in E[2]$, contradicting exact order 4. So $[-1]$ does not fix any $\Gamma_1(4)$ -structure.

Case $[\zeta_3]$ at $j = 0$. On the $j = 0$ elliptic curve the automorphism $[\zeta_3]$ is the standard $\mathbf{Z}[\zeta_3]$ -multiplication. In the $\mathbf{Z}[\zeta_3]$ -module $E[4]$ (well-defined since $\gcd(3, 4) = 1$), the endomorphism $\zeta_3 - 1 \in \mathbf{Z}[\zeta_3]$ has norm $|1 - \zeta_3|^2 = 3$. Since $\gcd(3, 4) = 1$, multiplication by $\zeta_3 - 1$ is invertible on $E[4]$. Hence $(\zeta_3 - 1)\beta(1) = 0$ forces $\beta(1) = 0$, contradicting that $\beta(1)$ has exact order 4. Therefore no nontrivial ζ_3 -action fixes β .

Case $[i]$ at $j = 1728$. The automorphism $[i]$ acts on the tangent space as multiplication by $i \in \mathbf{Z}_p$ (after possibly adjoining i ; for the moduli interpretation we may work over $\mathbf{Z}_p[i]$). Hence $[i]$ acts on $E[4]$ as multiplication by i . For $\beta(1) \in E[4]$ of exact order 4, $[i]\beta(1) = i \cdot \beta(1)$, which equals $\beta(1)$ only if $(i - 1)\beta(1) = 0$. Since $i - 1$ has norm 2 in $\mathbf{Z}[i]$, and $\gcd(2, 4) = 2 \neq 1$, this requires $\beta(1)$ to lie in the 2-torsion subgroup $E[2]$, contradicting exact order 4. The squared automorphism $[i]^2 = [-1]$ is handled by the first case, and $[i]^3 = [-i]$ is treated symmetrically. Hence no nontrivial element of μ_4 fixes β .

Thus the only automorphism fixing a $\Gamma_1(4)$ -structure is the identity, and Y is fine. Since $(4, 3p) = 1$, the map $Y \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_0(3)$ is representable and finite étale over the ordinary locus. On Y^{ord} , Katz's construction sends

$$(E, C_3, \beta) \longmapsto (E/C_p, \bar{C}_3, \bar{\beta}),$$

where β is the $\Gamma_1(4)$ -structure and $\bar{C}_3, \bar{\beta}$ are the images under the quotient isogeny $E \rightarrow E/C_p$. The subgroup C_3 and the $\Gamma_1(4)$ -structure transport isomorphically because their orders are prime to p .

Pull this construction back to $Y \times_{\mathcal{X}_0(3)} Y$. An S -point of this fibre product is one elliptic curve with one $\Gamma_0(3)$ -subgroup and two auxiliary $\Gamma_1(4)$ -rigidifications; the two projections to Y differ only by which rigidification is remembered. On the fine atlas Y , the two pullbacks of the canonical Frobenius lift along the two projections $Y \times_{\mathcal{X}_0(3)} Y \rightrightarrows Y$ agree because the canonical subgroup is functorial under isomorphisms of generalized elliptic curves (Katz [9, Theorem 3.10.7]). The normalized weight- k trace operator on ω^k is similarly compatible with these isomorphisms, since the quotient isogeny, the induced map on the Hodge bundle, and the sheaf trace are natural in the descent groupoid. Therefore Katz's construction gives a descent datum in the stack groupoid, with the cocycle on the triple fibre product inherited from functoriality of composition, and the Frobenius lift and normalized trace descend from Y^{ord} to $\mathcal{X}_0(3)^{\text{ord}}$.

For the stabilizer equivariance at P_- : choose a point of the atlas above P_- , represented by (E_0, C_3, β) . The order-3 stabilizer element $[\zeta_3]$ does not fix β ; rather it gives an arrow in the descent groupoid $(E_0, C_3, \beta) \rightarrow (E_0, C_3, [\zeta_3]\beta)$. By [Theorem 4.4](#), $[\zeta_3](C_p) = C_p$, so after quotienting by C_p the same arrow descends to $(E_0/C_p, \bar{C}_3, \bar{\beta}) \rightarrow (E_0/C_p, \bar{C}_3, [\zeta_3]\bar{\beta})$. Thus the descended Frobenius morphism commutes with the μ_3 -action in the quotient-stack chart. In coordinates, $\zeta_3^* \Phi^* r = \Phi^* \zeta_3^* r$, and since $\zeta_3^* r = \zeta_3 r$, this becomes $F(\zeta_3 r) = \zeta_3 F(r)$. Therefore $F(r)/r$ is μ_3 -invariant and lies in $\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]$. Finally, the canonical Frobenius lift reduces modulo p to absolute Frobenius on the special fibre, so $F(r) \equiv r^p \pmod{p}$. Because $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $r^p = r(r^3)^{(p-1)/3}$. Writing

$$G(s) = s^{(p-1)/3} + p\alpha_1(s) + p^2\alpha_2(s) + p^3\alpha_3(s) + O(p^4)$$

gives (1). □

Remark 4.6. $M = 4$ is a tool, not a property of the result. Any $M \geq 3$ with $(M, 3p) = 1$ killing $\{\pm 1\}$ produces the same descended operator: on $Y \times_{\mathcal{X}_0(3)} Y'$ for two such atlases Y, Y' , both lifts of the canonical Frobenius send (E, C_3, β, β') to $(E/C_p, \bar{C}_3, \bar{\beta}, \bar{\beta}')$, since the canonical subgroup is functorial in E alone and prime-to- $3p$ level structures transport isomorphically.

Remark 4.7. The elliptic curve E_0 with $j = 0$ has CM by $\mathbf{Z}[\zeta_3]$, and by Deuring's criterion has ordinary reduction at p if and only if p splits in $\mathbf{Z}[\zeta_3]$, i.e., $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Under the split-prime hypothesis Katz's canonical subgroup is therefore defined at P_- , and the descent of [Theorem 4.5](#) carries both the Frobenius lift Φ and the normalized weight-5 trace operator $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ to $\mathcal{X}_0(3)^{\text{ord}}$; the latter realizes Λ_p on q -expansions by [Theorem 4.9](#).

Remark 4.8 (Inert primes). For inert primes $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, the Frobenius acts on the character group of μ_3 by $\chi \mapsto \chi^p = \chi^{-1}$. The local Frobenius is therefore semilinear on the stabilizer character rather than preserving the weight-one character of r ; the split-prime normal form $r \cdot G(r^3)$ is unavailable. This mirrors the inert obstruction proved in [Section 5](#) via the q -side.

Lemma 4.9 (Descended Katz trace: local formula and q -expansion). *Let Φ be the descended canonical Frobenius lift on $\mathcal{X}_0(3)^{\text{ord}}$ from [Theorem 4.5](#). Let $A = \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]$ be the stack-local cover at P_- . Let e, e' be μ_3 -equivariant local generators of the weight-5, χ_3 line bundle near the source and target of Φ , and write*

$$\Phi^* e' = p^5 J_{\Phi} e, \quad J_{\Phi} \in A^{\times}.$$

Then $J_{\Phi} \in A^{\mu_3, \times} = \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]^{\times}$, and the descended normalized Katz trace is given locally by

$$(2) \quad \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(fe) = \frac{1}{p} \text{Tr}_{A/\Phi^*A}(J_{\Phi}^{-1}f)e'.$$

At the cusp ∞ , with Tate parameter q , the same descended operator acts on finite Laurent q -expansions by

$$\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5} \left(\sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_{pn} q^n = \Lambda_p \left(\sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^n \right).$$

Thus the stack-local formula at P_- and the Cartier operator on q -expansions are restrictions of one descended global operator.

Proof. The local formula follows from the definition of Katz's normalized trace. Since $\Phi^*e' = p^5 J_\Phi e$, $e = p^{-5} J_\Phi^{-1} \Phi^*e'$, so the sheaf trace on $\omega^{\otimes 5}(\chi_3)$ sends $fe = p^{-5} J_\Phi^{-1} f \Phi^*e'$ to $p^{-5} \text{Tr}_{A/\Phi^*A}(J_\Phi^{-1} f)e'$. Katz's normalized weight-5 trace is p^4 times this sheaf trace [9, §3.11], hence the coefficient is $p^4 p^{-5} = 1/p$.

The invariant property of J_Φ is forced by equivariance. If $\lambda \in \mu_3$, then Φ is μ_3 -equivariant by Theorem 4.5. The local generators e, e' have the same μ_3 -character, because they generate the same automorphic line bundle on source and target. Applying λ^* to $\Phi^*e' = p^5 J_\Phi e$ gives $\Phi^*(\lambda^*e') = p^5 \lambda^*(J_\Phi) \lambda^*e$. Since λ^*e and λ^*e' are multiplied by the same character, comparison gives $\lambda^*(J_\Phi) = J_\Phi$. Thus $J_\Phi \in A^{\mu_3} = \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]$. It is a unit because the canonical Frobenius is an isogeny of ordinary elliptic curves and the normalized pullback on the Hodge bundle is a unit after extracting the explicit factor p in weight 1.

Now restrict to the Tate chart at ∞ . The universal object is $\text{Tate}(q)$ with its $\Gamma_0(3)$ -subgroup. The canonical subgroup is μ_p , and the quotient is $\text{Tate}(q)/\mu_p \simeq \text{Tate}(q^p)$. For the invariant differential $\omega = dT/T$, the quotient map satisfies $\Phi^*\omega' = p\omega$. Thus in weight 5 we have $J_\Phi = 1$ on the Tate chart. Let $Q = q^p$. The extension of Laurent series rings is $\mathbf{Z}_p((Q)) \subset \mathbf{Z}_p((q))$, with basis $1, q, \dots, q^{p-1}$. Multiplication by q^a , $1 \leq a \leq p-1$, has trace 0 in this basis, while multiplication by $q^{pm} = Q^m$ has trace pQ^m . Hence

$$\text{Tr}_{\mathbf{Z}_p((q))/\mathbf{Z}_p((q^p))}(q^n) = \begin{cases} p q^{n/p}, & p \mid n, \\ 0, & p \nmid n. \end{cases}$$

The local formula therefore gives $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(\sum a_n q^n) = \frac{1}{p} \sum a_n \text{Tr}(q^n) = \sum a_{pn} q^n = \Lambda_p$. \square

Remark 4.10. $J_\Phi^{-1} \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]^\times$ is μ_3 -invariant of p -valuation 0, hence suppresses without affecting μ_3 -character, p -valuation, or r -exponent mod 3 in the pole-counting argument below.

4.2. Length-three Witt–Cartier pole estimate. We use throughout the local setup of Section 4.1: $A = \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]$, $\zeta_3 \cdot r = \zeta_3 r$, $\Phi^*r = F(r)$ as in (1), $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ as in Theorem 4.9, $C_0 = r^2 c(r^3)e$. By Theorem 4.10, J_Φ^{-1} is suppressed.

Recall ν_p, ϕ_p from Theorem 3.5: $\nu_p = e^{-U_p} = t(q^p)/t(q)^p$ and $\phi_p = \nu_p - 1 \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$.

Since $F(r) \equiv r^p \pmod{p}$, F is distinguished of Weierstrass degree p ; Weierstrass preparation makes A finite free of rank p over $\Phi^*A = \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[F(r)]]$. Write $R := F(r)$ for the target parameter.

Lemma 4.11 (Trace-residue formula on the tame μ_3 -chart). *Let $A = \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r]]$, let $F(r) \in rA$ be a Frobenius lift on A , i.e. $F(r) \equiv r^p \pmod{p}$. Thus F is distinguished of Weierstrass degree p ; set $R = F(r)$, so $B := \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[R]] \subset A$ is a finite flat extension of rank p . Let $J_\Phi(r) \in A^\times$ denote the Jacobian of Φ with respect to the chosen weight-5 trivialization e , so that the normalized weight-5 Katz trace satisfies $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(he) = (p^{-1} \text{Tr}_{A/B}(h J_\Phi^{-1})) e$ for h in the field of fractions of A . Then for every $K \geq 1$ and every $h \in \text{Frac}(A)$ with at worst a Laurent principal part at $r = 0$,*

$$(3) \quad [R^{-K}] \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(he) = \frac{1}{p} \text{Res}_{r=0}(h(r) J_\Phi(r)^{-1} F'(r) F(r)^{K-1} dr).$$

In particular $J_\Phi^{-1} \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]^\times$ is a μ_3 -invariant unit on the tame chart, so it does not affect the r -valuation, the p -valuation, or the μ_3 -character class of the residue integrand.

Proof. For the principal part at $R = 0$, the trace-residue formula for finite flat extensions of complete local rings (see [17, §3] or [8, Ch. III]) gives, for $K \geq 1$,

$$[R^{-K}] \text{Tr}_{A/B}(h) = [R^{-K}] \text{Res}_{r=0} \left(\frac{h(r) F'(r)}{R - F(r)} dr \right).$$

In the Laurent ring $A((R^{-1}))$,

$$\frac{1}{R - F(r)} = \frac{1}{R} \cdot \frac{1}{1 - F(r)/R} = \sum_{K \geq 1} F(r)^{K-1} R^{-K},$$

viewed as a formal expansion in the independent target variable R^{-1} in $A((R^{-1}))$; no ordinary r -order assertion on F is used. The required finiteness and rank- p trace are supplied by the Weierstrass degree- p property $F \equiv r^p \pmod{p}$. Therefore

$$[R^{-K}] \operatorname{Tr}_{A/B}(h) = \operatorname{Res}_{r=0}(h(r)F'(r)F(r)^{K-1} dr).$$

Replacing h by hJ_{Φ}^{-1} and dividing by p gives (3).

The statement on J_{Φ}^{-1} : by [Theorems 4.2](#) and [4.9](#), J_{Φ} is a unit on the tame μ_3 -chart and lies in the μ_3 -invariant subring $\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]$. As a unit in this subring it has r -valuation 0 and μ_3 -character class 0, and its constant term is a p -adic unit, so it has p -valuation 0. Therefore multiplying the integrand by J_{Φ}^{-1} preserves all three quantities used in the pole estimate. \square

Remark 4.12 (Sign bookkeeping). If one writes the trace-residue formula with denominator $F(r) - R$, an overall minus sign must be inserted:

$$[R^{-K}] \operatorname{Tr}_{A/B}(h) = -[R^{-K}] \operatorname{Res}_{r=0} \left(\frac{h(r)F'(r)}{F(r) - R} dr \right).$$

Together with

$$\frac{1}{F(r) - R} = - \sum_{K \geq 1} F(r)^{K-1} R^{-K},$$

this gives the same positive coefficient formula (3). The pole estimate uses only valuations and μ_3 -character classes, but the displayed coefficient identity is fixed with the positive sign.

Proposition 4.13 (Length-three Witt–Cartier pole estimate). *For every $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and every s with $\ell \leq s \leq 3$,*

$$(4) \quad p^{s-\ell} \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(r^{2+s(1-p)} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]] e) \subset r^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]] e \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

Proof. By [Theorem 4.11](#), the principal-part coefficient in R is

$$(5) \quad [R^{-K}] \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(fe) = \frac{1}{p} \operatorname{Res}_{r=0}(f(r) J_{\Phi}(r)^{-1} F'(r) F(r)^{K-1} dr),$$

where $J_{\Phi}^{-1} \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]^{\times}$ has r -valuation 0, p -valuation 0, and μ_3 -character class 0, hence does not affect the estimates below; we suppress it in the rest of the proof and refer to [Theorem 4.11](#) for justification. After identifying the target completed disk with $\operatorname{Spf} A$ and relabelling R back to r , this is the r^{-K} coefficient.

Step 1: $\mathbb{Z}/3$ -counting forces $K \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. $f \in r^{2+s(1-p)} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]$ contributes r -exponent $\equiv 2 + s(1-p) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ since $1-p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. The derivative

$$F'(r) = p r^{p-1} + p D_1(r) + p^2 D_2(r) + p^3 D_3(r), \quad D_i(r) = \alpha_i(r^3) + 3r^3 \alpha'_i(r^3),$$

has both terms in exponent class $\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. The factor $F(r)^{K-1}$ has each factor of F in class $\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, so contributes $\equiv K-1 \pmod{3}$. A nonzero residue requires total exponent $-1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, giving $2 + 0 + (K-1) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, hence $K \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. For $K \geq 2$ this forces $K \geq 4$.

Step 2: Valuation count. Write $F(r)^{K-1} = r^{p(K-1)}(1+X)^{K-1}$ with $X = pr^{1-p}\alpha_1 + p^2r^{1-p}\alpha_2 + p^3r^{1-p}\alpha_3$. The binomial expansion selects $b \leq K-1$ factors of X , each contributing minimal r -exponent $1-p$ and p -valuation at least 1.

Derivative-high case ($F' \rightarrow pr^{p-1}$): total r -exponent

$$E_{\text{high}} = 2 + s(1-p) + (p-1) + p(K-1) + b(1-p) + 3h = 1 + s + b + p(K-b-s) + 3h$$

with $h \geq 0$. Residue condition $E_{\text{high}} = -1$:

$$(p-1)(s+b) = pK + 2 + 3h, \quad s+b-K = \frac{K+2+3h}{p-1} > 0,$$

hence $s+b \geq K+1$, so $b \geq K+1-s$. With $K \geq 4$, $b \geq 5-s$.

Derivative-low case ($F' \rightarrow p^j D_j$, $j \geq 1$): similar computation gives

$$(p-1)(s+b) = p(K-1) + 3 + 3h, \quad s+b-(K-1) = \frac{K+2+3h}{p-1} > 0,$$

hence $s+b \geq K$ and $b \geq K-s \geq 4-s$ when $K \geq 4$.

Control example ($p=7$, $K=4$, $s=1$, $h=0$): low case requires $6(s+b) = 24$, so $s+b=4$ and $b=3$, satisfying $b \leq K-1=3$. High case requires $6(s+b) = 30$, so $b=4 > K-1=3$, hence does not occur in this minimal example.

Step 3: Total valuation. Before the external $1/p$, each integrand has p -valuation $\geq 1+b$ (the explicit p from F' plus at least b from the X -expansion). After $1/p$, valuation $\geq b \geq 4-s$ (the minimum, from the low case). Multiplying by external $p^{s-\ell}$ in (4) gives valuation $\geq (4-s)+(s-\ell) = 4-\ell$. Thus every r^{-K} coefficient with $K \geq 2$ vanishes mod $p^{4-\ell}$.

The suppressed $O(p^4)$ part of F contributes valuation ≥ 4 before $1/p$, hence ≥ 3 after, already vanishing for all $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Step 4: $K=1$. $F^{K-1} = 1$, and the residue lands in the r^{-1} part of the principal part. Combining steps gives (4). \square

Remark 4.14 (The role of the $\mathbb{Z}/3$ -counting). Without the μ_3 -equivariant congruence-class exclusion, the residue calculation would not rule out the lower principal parts $K=2, 3$. The split CM argument gains its extra digit precisely by excluding those two possibilities and forcing $K \geq 4$; this is the local mechanism behind the improvement from the generic weight-3 expectation p^3 [14] to the p^4 estimate proved here.

4.3. Hecke finite differences and Cartier–Hecke comparison. For $\ell = 1, 2, 3$ define first the Hecke finite-difference numerator for C_0 :

$$(6) \quad N_\ell(C_0) := \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j T_p \left(\frac{C_0}{t^j p} \right),$$

where T_p is the Hecke operator on weakly holomorphic weight-5, χ_3 forms. After the global divisibility statement of Theorem 4.17, we write

$$(7) \quad \mathfrak{E}_\ell := N_\ell(C_0)/p^\ell.$$

Lemma 4.15 (Hecke action on weakly holomorphic forms). *Let f be a weight-5, χ_3 form on $\Gamma_0(3)$ over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$, weakly holomorphic with finite principal parts at both cusps: $f|_\infty = \sum_{n \geq -m_\infty} a_n q^n$ and $f|_0 = \sum_{n \geq -m_0} b_n q_0^n$. Then the Hecke operator T_p (where $p \neq 3$ prime) defined via the double coset $\Gamma_0(3) \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix} \Gamma_0(3)$ acting in weight 5 with character χ_3 [2, §5], [6, §5.1] preserves the space of such forms and on the cusp- ∞ q -expansion is given by*

$$T_p f(q) = \sum_n a_{pn} q^n + \chi_3(p) p^4 \sum_n a_n q^{pn}.$$

At split primes $\chi_3(p) = 1$ this reads $T_p f = \Lambda_p f + p^4 \text{Ver}_p(f)$ where $\text{Ver}_p(f)(q) = f(q^p)$. The operator preserves $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -integrality and commutes with reduction modulo p^k for every $k \geq 1$.

Proof. Let $X = X_0(3)_{\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}}$ and let $\omega^5(\chi_3)$ denote the corresponding automorphic line bundle of weight 5 and character χ_3 . The Hecke correspondence

$$X \xleftarrow{\pi_1} X_0(3p) \xrightarrow{\pi_2} X$$

with $(p, 3) = 1$ is a finite flat correspondence over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$, étale on the generic fibre and on the étale (Verschiebung) component over the ordinary locus, away from the supersingular and cusp loci. It has finite degree on the compact curve. The pullback π_1^* and the trace $(\pi_2)_*$ send weakly holomorphic sections of $\omega^5(\chi_3)$ to weakly holomorphic sections; this is because both maps are finite morphisms of compact curves and therefore preserve sections with poles supported on the cuspidal locus (the only divisorial poles of weakly holomorphic forms). Hence $T_p := (\pi_2)_*\pi_1^*$ preserves the space of weakly holomorphic weight-5, χ_3 forms over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$.

To compute the q -expansion at the cusp ∞ on Laurent expansions, we use the standard double-coset description of the Hecke operator. For $p \neq 3$, by [6, Lem. 5.1.1 and Prop. 5.2.1] (which describe the double-coset decomposition on $\Gamma_0(3)$ and the action of $\Gamma_0(3)\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & p \end{smallmatrix}\right)\Gamma_0(3)$ in weight k with character χ), the orbits split as

$$\Gamma_0(3)\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & p \end{smallmatrix}\right)\Gamma_0(3) = \bigsqcup_{j=0}^{p-1} \Gamma_0(3)\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 1 & j \\ 0 & p \end{smallmatrix}\right) \sqcup \Gamma_0(3)\left(\begin{smallmatrix} p & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{smallmatrix}\right),$$

each $j \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}$ contributing $p^{-1} \sum_j f((\tau+j)/p)$ and the last orbit contributing $p^{k-1} \chi(p) f(p\tau)$ in weight k . Apply this in weight $k = 5$ and character χ_3 ; expand $f|_\infty = \sum_n a_n q^n$ with $q = e^{2\pi i \tau}$. The sum $\sum_{j=0}^{p-1} e^{2\pi i n(\tau+j)/p}$ equals $p \cdot q^{n/p}$ when $p \mid n$ and 0 otherwise, so the first set of orbits contributes $\sum_{p|n} a_n q^{n/p} = \sum_n a_{pn} q^n = \Lambda_p f(q)$. The last orbit contributes $p^{k-1} \chi_3(p) f(p\tau) = p^4 \chi_3(p) \sum_n a_n q^{pn} = p^4 \chi_3(p) \text{Ver}_p f(q)$. Combining gives the displayed formula.

The same derivation applies on Laurent series with finite principal parts, since the orbit sums are linear in the input and the formulas Λ_p and Ver_p extend coefficient-wise to Laurent series: if f has principal part $\sum_{n=-m_\infty}^{-1} a_n q^n$, then $\Lambda_p f$ has principal part of length $\leq \lceil m_\infty/p \rceil$, and $\text{Ver}_p f$ has principal part of length pm_∞ . Hence T_p sends weakly holomorphic forms to weakly holomorphic forms at the cusp ∞ ; by symmetric argument applied via the Fricke involution w_3 , the same holds at the cusp 0. (For an exposition of the weakly holomorphic version of the Hecke formalism applied to modular forms with finite principal parts, see [7, §2].)

Integrality over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ is immediate from the formula since $a_n \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ and the operations Λ_p , Ver_p preserve $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -coefficients; commutation with reduction modulo p^k follows since T_p is a $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -linear operator. At split primes $\chi_3(p) = 1$. \square

Lemma 4.16 (Saturated weak q -expansion lattice). *Let $R = \mathbf{Z}_p$, $p \geq 7$, and let D be a horizontal effective Cartier divisor on $\mathcal{X}_0(3)_R$ supported on P_∞, P_0, P_- . Put*

$$L_D := H^0(\mathcal{X}_0(3)_R, \omega^5(\chi_3)(D)).$$

If $s \in L_D \otimes_R \mathbf{Q}_p$ has Laurent q -expansion at P_∞ in $R((q))$, then $s \in L_D$.

Proof. It is enough to prove that the q -expansion map

$$L_D/pL_D \longrightarrow \mathbf{F}_p((q))$$

is injective. Let $\mathcal{L} = \omega^5(\chi_3)(D)$. The special fibre of the rigidified stack is integral, with trivial generic stabilizer, and the cusp P_∞ is a non-stacky smooth point. From the reduction exact sequence

$$0 \longrightarrow \mathcal{L} \xrightarrow{p} \mathcal{L} \longrightarrow \mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{F}_p} \longrightarrow 0$$

the map $L_D/pL_D \hookrightarrow H^0(\mathcal{X}_{\mathbf{F}_p}, \mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{F}_p})$ is injective. If \bar{s} has zero Laurent q -expansion at P_∞ , then its germ in the completed local ring at P_∞ vanishes. Since $\mathcal{X}_{\mathbf{F}_p}$ is integral and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{F}_p}$ is invertible, \bar{s} is zero as a rational section, hence $\bar{s} = 0$. The stacky point P_- only imposes the μ_3 -eigenspace condition in the local chart $[\text{Spf } \mathbf{F}_p[[r]]/\mu_3]$ (the line $r^2 \mathbf{F}_p[[r^3]]$ for weight 5 and character χ_3); this is a local restriction and does not produce sections supported at P_- alone.

Now let $s \in L_D \otimes_R \mathbf{Q}_p$ have q -expansion in $R((q))$. Choose $a \geq 0$ minimal with $p^a s \in L_D$. If $a > 0$, then the q -expansion of $p^a s$ is zero modulo p . By injectivity, $p^a s \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ in L_D/pL_D , contradicting the minimality of a . Hence $a = 0$, and $s \in L_D$. \square

Lemma 4.17 (Divisibility of the Hecke finite-difference numerator). *Let $p \geq 7$ be split, let $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$, and let $\ell = 1, 2, 3$. Define*

$$N_\ell(f) := \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j T_p \left(\frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right).$$

Then there is a horizontal effective Cartier divisor $D_{\ell,p}$ supported on P_∞, P_0, P_- such that

$$N_\ell(f) \in p^\ell H^0(\mathcal{X}_0(3)_{\mathbf{Z}_p}, \omega^5(\chi_3)(D_{\ell,p})).$$

Consequently $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) := N_\ell(f)/p^\ell$ is an integral weakly holomorphic weight-5, χ_3 section with polar support contained in $\{P_\infty, P_0, P_-\}$.

Proof. By [Theorem 4.25](#), the rational function $t = u/(1+27u)^2$ has divisor $P_\infty + P_0 - 2P_-$. Thus each f/t^{jp} has only finite principal parts at the two cusps and no pole away from them. By [Theorem 4.15](#), $T_p(f/t^{jp})$ is an integral weakly holomorphic section. Multiplication by t^j can introduce only poles supported on P_∞, P_0, P_- . Hence, for a sufficiently large horizontal effective Cartier divisor $D_{\ell,p}$ supported on these three points, $N_\ell(f)$ lies in the integral lattice

$$L_{D_{\ell,p}} := H^0(\mathcal{X}_0(3)_{\mathbf{Z}_p}, \omega^5(\chi_3)(D_{\ell,p})).$$

It remains to prove divisibility by p^ℓ in this lattice. On the q -expansion at P_∞ , use $T_p = \Lambda_p + p^4 \text{Ver}_p$ from [Theorem 4.15](#). For the Cartier part, [Theorem 3.4](#) gives

$$t^j \Lambda_p \left(\frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right) = \Lambda_p \left(\sigma_p(t^j) \frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right) = \Lambda_p(f \nu_p^j),$$

where $\nu_p = t(q^p)/t(q)^p = 1 + \phi_p$. Therefore

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j \Lambda_p \left(\frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right) = \Lambda_p(f(\nu_p - 1)^\ell) = \Lambda_p(f \phi_p^\ell).$$

Since $\phi_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_p[[q]]$, this Laurent expansion lies in $p^\ell \mathbf{Z}_p((q))$.

The Verschiebung part is

$$p^4 \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t(q)^j \text{Ver}_p \left(\frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right),$$

which is p^4 times an integral Laurent series, hence lies in $p^\ell \mathbf{Z}_p((q))$ for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$. Thus the q -expansion of $N_\ell(f)/p^\ell$ lies in $\mathbf{Z}_p((q))$. Applying [Theorem 4.16](#) to $N_\ell(f)/p^\ell \in L_{D_{\ell,p}} \otimes \mathbf{Q}_p$ proves the asserted global divisibility. \square

Lemma 4.18 (Local Cartier–Hecke comparison on the ordinary locus). *Let $p \geq 7$ be split, let $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$, and let $\ell = 1, 2, 3$. Put*

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) := \frac{N_\ell(f)}{p^\ell},$$

where the quotient is the integral global weak section supplied by [Theorem 4.17](#). For $f = C_0$ this is the finite difference \mathfrak{E}_ℓ of [\(7\)](#); for $f = uC_0$ write \mathfrak{E}'_ℓ . Let $\nu_\Phi := \Phi^ t/t^p$ and $\psi := (\nu_\Phi - 1)/p$. As meromorphic weight-5, χ_3 sections on the ordinary locus, the identity*

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) - \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) = p^{4-\ell} \mathcal{V}_\ell(f)$$

holds, where

$$\mathcal{V}_\ell(f) := \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j \text{Ver}_p(f/t^{jp})$$

is a meromorphic weight-5, χ_3 section on the ordinary locus with $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -integral coefficients. In particular, on the ordinary locus,

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \equiv \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

On q -expansions at the cusp ∞ this reads

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \equiv \Lambda_p \left(f \frac{\phi_p^\ell}{p^\ell} \right) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}},$$

because $\nu_\Phi(q) = t(q^p)/t(q)^p$ and $\phi_p = \nu_\Phi - 1$ on the Tate chart.

Proof. Target-linearity of the trace: if a is a meromorphic function on the target and h a meromorphic weight-5 section on the source, then $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}((\Phi^*a)h) = a\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(h)$, because $\text{Tr}_{A/\Phi^*A}((\Phi^*a)b) = a \text{Tr}_{A/\Phi^*A}(b)$. By Katz's construction of the ordinary U -operator as normalized trace [9, §3.11], pulled back to the fine atlas Y and descended by Theorem 4.5, the classical prime-to-3 Hecke operator decomposes on the ordinary locus as

$$T_p = \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5} + \chi_3(p)p^4 \text{Ver}_p,$$

where Ver_p is the Verschiebung operator with q -expansion $h(q) \mapsto h(q^p)$. At split primes $\chi_3(p) = 1$. Expanding $\psi^\ell = p^{-\ell} \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} (\Phi^*t)^j/t^{jp}$, applying $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ and using target-linearity gives

$$\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) = \frac{1}{p^\ell} \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5} \left(\frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right).$$

Replacing $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ by $T_p - p^4 \text{Ver}_p$ gives

$$\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) = \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) - p^{4-\ell} \mathcal{V}_\ell(f),$$

which is the displayed local identity. $\mathcal{V}_\ell(f)$ has integral coefficients since Ver_p acts by q^p -substitution preserving $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -coefficients, and each t^j is integral on the open subscheme where t is regular (and at worst has poles at P_0, P_- , controlled later). By Theorem 4.9, the q -expansion of $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ at ∞ is Λ_p , and on that chart $\nu_\Phi(q) = t(q^p)/t(q)^p$, so $\nu_\Phi - 1 = \phi_p$. This gives the displayed q -expansion form. \square

Lemma 4.19 (Holomorphy transfer for the finite differences). *Let $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$ and $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, and set $S := \mathbf{Z}_p/p^{4-\ell}\mathbf{Z}_p$. Then $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ reduces to an element of $M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) \otimes S$, where $g = 1+27u$.*

Proof. Step 1: Global divided section. Define the numerator

$$N_\ell(f) := \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j T_p \left(\frac{f}{t^{jp}} \right).$$

By Theorem 4.17, there is an effective divisor $D_{\ell,p}$ supported on P_∞, P_0, P_- such that

$$N_\ell(f) \in p^\ell H^0(\mathcal{X}_0(3)_{\mathbf{Z}_p}, \omega^5(\chi_3)(D_{\ell,p})).$$

We therefore define

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) := N_\ell(f)/p^\ell$$

as an integral global weakly holomorphic section. Its polar support is contained in $\{P_\infty, P_0, P_-\}$.

Step 2: Local holomorphy of $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ at P_∞ . On the Tate chart at ∞ , $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \equiv \Lambda_p(f \phi_p^\ell/p^\ell) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$ by Theorem 4.18. By Theorems 3.3 and 3.5, $\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell \in q^\ell \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, hence $f \phi_p^\ell/p^\ell \in q \mathbf{Z}_p[[q]]$, hence Λ_p of this lies in $q \mathbf{Z}_p[[q]]$, hence $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \in q \mathbf{Z}_p[[q]] \otimes S$ at the cusp ∞ .

Step 3: Local holomorphy of $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ at P_0 . On the Fricke–Tate chart at 0, by [Theorem 4.22](#), $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) \in q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$. By [Theorem 4.18](#), the local identity $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \equiv \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$ holds on the cusp-0 Tate chart (which is part of the ordinary locus since $p \nmid 3$). Multiplying by $g \in \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]] \cdot 27u^{-1} + \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$ (a function with at worst a simple pole at P_0) yields a series in $\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]] \otimes S$. The explicit computation in [Theorem 4.22](#) confirms this.

Step 4: Local holomorphy of $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ at P_- . By [Theorem 4.24](#), $\text{pole}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)) \leq 1 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$ for both $f = C_0$ and $f = uC_0$. Since g has a simple zero at P_- (i.e., $\text{ord}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(g) = 3$ on the stack and $\text{ord}_{P_-}(g) = 1$ on the coarse curve), $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ has $\text{pole}_{P_-}^{\text{st}} \leq 0$ modulo $p^{4-\ell}$, i.e., is regular at P_- .

Conclusion. Steps 2–4 establish that the polar divisor of $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ modulo $p^{4-\ell}$ is empty at each of P_∞, P_0, P_- . By Step 1 these are the only possible poles. Therefore $g \mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ is globally holomorphic of weight 5 and character χ_3 modulo $p^{4-\ell}$, i.e., it represents an element of $M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) \otimes S$. \square

Lemma 4.20 (Cusp-0 regularity of ϕ_p^ℓ). *Let q_0 be the Fricke–Tate parameter at the cusp 0, normalized so that $w_3^*q = q_0$. Then $t = q_0\eta_0(q_0)$ with $\eta_0(q_0) \in 1 + q_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$, and Katz’s canonical Frobenius satisfies $\Phi^*q_0 = q_0^p$ on the completed local ring at cusp 0. Consequently*

$$\phi_p = \frac{\Phi^*t}{t^p} - 1 \in pq_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]],$$

and therefore $\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell \in q_0^\ell\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$ for $\ell \geq 1$.

Proof. At ∞ one has $u = q + O(q^2)$ and $t = u/(1 + 27u)^2 = q + O(q^2)$. The Fricke involution exchanges ∞ and 0, and t is w_3 -invariant. Hence, in the Fricke–Tate parameter $q_0 = w_3^*q$ at cusp 0, $t = q_0\eta_0(q_0)$ with $\eta_0(q_0) \in 1 + q_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$. The cusp 0 is described by the Tate curve $\text{Tate}(q_0)$ in the Fricke chart with its transported $\Gamma_0(3)$ -subgroup. Since $p \nmid 3$, the canonical subgroup of $\text{Tate}(q_0)$ is μ_p , and $\text{Tate}(q_0)/\mu_p \simeq \text{Tate}(q_0^p)$. The $\Gamma_0(3)$ -subgroup transports isomorphically. Thus Katz’s canonical Frobenius is $q_0 \mapsto q_0^p$ on the completed local ring at cusp 0. Now compute

$$\frac{\Phi^*t}{t^p} = \frac{q_0^p \eta_0(q_0^p)}{q_0^p \eta_0(q_0)^p} = \frac{\eta_0(q_0^p)}{\eta_0(q_0)^p}.$$

Since $\eta_0(q_0) \in 1 + q_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$, coefficientwise Frobenius gives $\eta_0(q_0)^p \equiv \eta_0(q_0^p) \pmod{p}$. Therefore $\Phi^*t/t^p \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Its constant term is also 1, so $\phi_p \in p\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]] \cap q_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]] = pq_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$. Raising to the ℓ -th power and dividing by p^ℓ gives $\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell \in q_0^\ell\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$. \square

Lemma 4.21 (Cartier expansion at the cusp 0). *On the Fricke–Tate chart at the cusp 0, with parameter q_0 , the normalized weight-5 Katz trace attached to Φ is the Cartier operator*

$$\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5} \left(\sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q_0^n \right) = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_{pn} q_0^n.$$

In particular it preserves the ideal $q_0\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$. Moreover, on this chart

$$\psi = \frac{\Phi^*t/t^p - 1}{p} = \frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{t(q_0^p)}{t(q_0)^p} - 1 \right).$$

Proof. By [Theorem 4.20](#), Katz’s canonical Frobenius is $q_0 \mapsto q_0^p$ on the completed local ring at the cusp 0. The same Tate-curve calculation as in [Theorem 4.9](#) applies in the Fricke–Tate coordinate: for the invariant differential $\omega = dT/T$, the quotient by the canonical subgroup satisfies $\Phi^*\omega' = p\omega$, so the weight-5 normalization contributes the same factor as at ∞ . Thus the normalized trace is

$$\frac{1}{p} \text{Tr}_{\mathbf{Z}_p((q_0))/\mathbf{Z}_p((q_0^p))}.$$

For $Q_0 = q_0^p$, the extension $\mathbf{Z}_p((Q_0)) \subset \mathbf{Z}_p((q_0))$ has basis $1, q_0, \dots, q_0^{p-1}$, and hence

$$\mathrm{Tr}(q_0^n) = \begin{cases} p q_0^{n/p}, & p \mid n, \\ 0, & p \nmid n. \end{cases}$$

Dividing by p gives the displayed Cartier formula, and preservation of $q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$ is immediate since $pn \geq p \geq 7 > 0$ forces $n \geq 1$ in any nonzero output term. The formula for ψ is the definition $\psi = (\Phi^* t/t^p - 1)/p$ together with $\Phi^* q_0 = q_0^p$. \square

Lemma 4.22 (Cusp-0 regularity on the two Eisenstein lines). *Let $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$ and $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Set $\phi_{p,0} := t(q_0^p)/t(q_0)^p - 1$. On the Fricke–Tate chart at the cusp 0,*

$$f \cdot \frac{\phi_{p,0}^\ell}{p^\ell} \in q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]].$$

Consequently the normalized Katz trace satisfies $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) \in q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$ on the cusp-0 Tate chart, and therefore $g\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell)$ is holomorphic at the cusp 0, where $g = 1 + 27u$ as in the Notation.

Proof. By [Theorem 4.25](#), $\mathrm{ord}_0(C_0) = 1$ and $\mathrm{ord}_0(uC_0) = 0$, with S -unit leading coefficients. By the proof of [Theorem 4.20](#), applied in the Fricke–Tate coordinate, the local defect

$$\phi_{p,0} := t(q_0^p)/t(q_0)^p - 1$$

lies in $pq_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$, so $\phi_{p,0}^\ell/p^\ell \in q_0^\ell \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$ for $\ell \geq 1$. Multiplying:

$$\mathrm{ord}_0\left(C_0 \cdot \phi_{p,0}^\ell/p^\ell\right) \geq 1 + \ell \geq 2, \quad \mathrm{ord}_0\left(uC_0 \cdot \phi_{p,0}^\ell/p^\ell\right) \geq \ell \geq 1.$$

In particular both products lie in $q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$. By [Theorem 4.21](#), the normalized Katz trace on the cusp-0 chart is the Cartier operator for $q_0 \mapsto q_0^p$, and it preserves $q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$; since on this chart $\psi = \phi_{p,0}/p$ by the same lemma, this gives $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) \in q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$.

Finally, $\mathrm{ord}_0(g) = \mathrm{ord}_0(1 + 27u) = -1$ because $\mathrm{ord}_0(u) = -1$ with S -unit leading coefficient ([Theorem 4.25](#)). Hence multiplying an element of $q_0 \mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$ by g yields an element of $\mathbf{Z}_p[[q_0]]$, i.e., a holomorphic q_0 -series at the cusp 0. \square

4.4. Classicality on both basis elements.

Lemma 4.23 (Layer decomposition of $\Phi^* t/t^p - 1$ at P_-). *On the formal completion at P_- with stack parameter r and $s = r^3$, write*

$$\Phi^* r = F(r) = r^p + \sum_{j \geq 1} p^j r \alpha_j(r^3), \quad \alpha_j \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]].$$

Then

$$\frac{\Phi^* t}{t^p} - 1 = pA_1(r) + p^2 A_2(r) + p^3 A_3(r) + O(p^4),$$

where $A_j(r) \in r^{j(1-p)} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]]$ for $j = 1, 2, 3$.

Proof. With the normalization $g = 1 + 27u = r^3 = s$, one has

$$t = \frac{u}{g^2} = r^{-6} \tau(s), \quad \tau(s) = \frac{s-1}{27} \in \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]]^\times.$$

Put

$$Y := \frac{F(r)}{r^p} - 1 = pY_1 + p^2 Y_2 + p^3 Y_3 + O(p^4), \quad Y_j \in r^{1-p} \mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]].$$

Then

$$\frac{\Phi^* t}{t^p} = (1 + Y)^{-6} \cdot \frac{\tau(F(r)^3)}{\tau(s)^p}.$$

The first factor has the binomial expansion

$$(1 + Y)^{-6} = 1 + pB_1 + p^2B_2 + p^3B_3 + O(p^4), \quad B_j \in r^{j(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]].$$

For the second factor, since $F(r)^3 = s^p(1 + Y)^3$ and $\tau(s) = (s - 1)/27$,

$$\frac{\tau(F(r)^3)}{\tau(s)^p} = 27^{p-1} \frac{s^p(1 + Y)^3 - 1}{(s - 1)^p}.$$

The term with $Y = 0$ is congruent to 1 modulo p , because $s^p - 1 \equiv (s - 1)^p \pmod{p}$ and $27^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$; its higher p -adic coefficients lie in $\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]]$, which is contained in $r^{j(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]]$ for every $j \geq 1$. The remaining terms contain $(1 + Y)^3 - 1$, whose degree- j contribution lies in $p^j r^{j(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]]$; multiplication by $s^p/(s - 1)^p$ preserves these inclusions. Hence

$$\frac{\tau(F(r)^3)}{\tau(s)^p} = 1 + pC_1 + p^2C_2 + p^3C_3 + O(p^4), \quad C_j \in r^{j(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[s]].$$

Multiplying the two expansions gives the asserted layer decomposition. \square

Lemma 4.24 (Stack pole bound on the two Eisenstein lines). *Let $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$, and let $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ be the finite difference of Theorem 4.18. Then, for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$,*

$$\text{pole}_{P_-}^{\text{st}}(\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)) \leq 1 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

Proof. Set $\psi := (\Phi^*t/t^p - 1)/p$. By Theorem 4.23,

$$\psi \in r^{1-p}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]] + pr^{2(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]] + p^2r^{3(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[\zeta_3][[r^3]] \pmod{p^3}.$$

At P_- , the divisor chart gives

$$C_0 = r^2c(r^3)e, \quad uC_0 = r^2c_u(r^3)e,$$

with $c(0), c_u(0) \in \mathbf{Z}_p^\times$, since u is a unit at P_- (Theorem 4.25). Thus the same estimate applies to both $f = C_0$ and $f = uC_0$. Hence $f\psi^\ell = \sum_{s=\ell}^3 p^{s-\ell} F_{\ell,s}(r)e \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$, $F_{\ell,s} \in r^{2+s(1-p)}\mathbf{Z}_p[[r^3]]$. By Theorem 4.13, each summand maps under $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}$ into $r^{-1}\mathbf{Z}_p[[r^3]]e \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$. By the local Cartier–Hecke comparison Theorem 4.18, on the ordinary neighbourhood of P_- (which is ordinary at split primes since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ makes $j = 0$ split-ordinary),

$$\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f) \equiv \mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell) \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

Hence the r^{-1} -pole bound established for $\mathcal{C}_{\Phi,5}(f\psi^\ell)$ above transfers to $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ modulo $p^{4-\ell}$. The displayed q -expansion identity is the Tate-chart specialization at the cusp ∞ and is not used here. \square

Lemma 4.25 (Level-3 divisor chart for C_0 and uC_0). *Let $p \geq 7$ be split, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, let $R = \mathbf{Z}_p$, and let S be either R or $R/p^N R$. Let P_∞ denote the cusp with $q = 0$ so that $u(P_\infty) = 0$, let P_0 denote the other cusp so that $u = \infty$, and let $P_- : 1 + 27u = 0$. On the coarse curve $X_0(3)_S \simeq \mathbb{P}_{u,S}^1$ the following local order table holds:*

	P_∞	P_0	P_-
u	1	-1	0
C_0	0	1	2 (stack)
uC_0	1	0	2 (stack).

Moreover the leading coefficients in all three local descriptions are S -units. In particular C_0 has no zero away from P_0 and P_- , and uC_0 is holomorphic at all three special points.

Proof. This is Theorem 2.3. \square

Lemma 4.26 (Integral basis and mod p^N classicality on $M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$). *Let $p \geq 7$ be split, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and let $R = \mathbf{Z}_p$. For $S = R$ or $S = R/p^N R$, put*

$$\mathcal{X}_S := \mathcal{X}_0(3) \times_{\text{Spec } R} \text{Spec } S, \quad \mathcal{L}_S := \omega^5(\chi_3)|_{\mathcal{X}_S}, \quad M_5(S) := H^0(\mathcal{X}_S, \mathcal{L}_S).$$

Then the S -linear map $S^2 \rightarrow M_5(S)$, $(a, b) \mapsto aC_0 + buC_0$, is an isomorphism. Equivalently, $M_5(S) = SC_0 \oplus SuC_0$. In particular for every $N \geq 1$, $M_5(R/p^N R) = (R/p^N R)C_0 \oplus (R/p^N R)uC_0$, and the q -expansion map at P_∞ is injective on $M_5(R/p^N R)$, with image the $(R/p^N R)$ -span of $C_0(q)$ and $u(q)C_0(q)$.

Proof. By [Theorem 4.25](#) both C_0 and uC_0 are holomorphic sections of \mathcal{L}_S . Let $f \in M_5(S)$. We show f/C_0 is a section of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbb{P}_S^1}(P_0)$ on the coarse curve. On the non-stacky points away from the zeros of C_0 , f/C_0 is regular. The only finite zero of C_0 is at P_- . Near P_- we use the quotient-stack chart $\widehat{\mathcal{X}}_{S, P_-} \simeq [\text{Spf } S[[r]]/\mu_3]$, $s = r^3$. Choose the local generator e of \mathcal{L}_S so that $C_0 = r^2c(s)e$, $c(0) \in S^\times$. If $f = F(r)e$ is an invariant local section, then $F(r)$ lies in the same μ_3 -eigenspace as $r^2c(s)$, because f and C_0 are sections of the same equivariant line bundle. Since $S[[r]] = S[[s]] \oplus rS[[s]] \oplus r^2S[[s]]$ and $3 \in S^\times$, this eigenspace is exactly $r^2S[[s]]$. Thus $F(r) = r^2d(s)$, $d(s) \in S[[s]]$, and $f/C_0 = d(s)/c(s) \in S[[s]]$. Therefore f/C_0 is regular at P_- .

At P_∞ the section C_0 is a unit, so f/C_0 is regular. On the affine coarse chart $\mathbb{A}_{u, S}^1 = \text{Spec } S[u]$, $f/C_0 \in S[u]$. At P_0 , write $v = 1/u$. By [Theorem 4.25](#), $C_0 = vc_0(v)e_0$, $c_0(0) \in S^\times$. For $f = F_0(v)e_0$ with $F_0(v) \in S[[v]]$, $v \cdot f/C_0 = F_0(v)/c_0(v) \in S[[v]]$. Thus f/C_0 has pole order at most 1 at P_0 and no other pole.

It remains to compute $H^0(\mathbb{P}_S^1, \mathcal{O}(P_0)) = S[u] \cap v^{-1}S[v]$. Since $v^{-1}S[v] = S[u^{-1}] + S \cdot u$ and the Laurent monomials are S -linearly independent, the intersection is $S \oplus S \cdot u$. Hence $f/C_0 = a + bu$, $a, b \in S$, and $f = aC_0 + buC_0$. This proves surjectivity.

For injectivity and the q -expansion statement, use $C_0(q) = 1 + O(q)$ and $u(q)C_0(q) = q + O(q^2)$. The matrix $\begin{pmatrix} [q^0]C_0 & [q^0](uC_0) \\ [q^1]C_0 & [q^1](uC_0) \end{pmatrix}$ has $[q^0](uC_0) = 0$ and $[q^0]C_0 = [q^1](uC_0) = 1$, hence determinant 1. Thus if $aC_0 + buC_0$ has zero q -expansion over S , the constant term gives $a = 0$, and the q^1 coefficient then gives $b = 0$. Taking $S = R$ gives the integral free R -basis, and taking $S = R/p^N R$ gives the asserted mod p^N classicality. \square

Theorem 4.27 (Closure for C_0). *For every split prime $p \geq 7$ and every $\ell = 1, 2, 3$,*

$$g\Lambda_p(C_0\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell) \in (\mathbf{Z}_p/p^{4-\ell}\mathbf{Z}_p) \cdot uC_0.$$

Proof. Set $S = R/p^{4-\ell}R$. By [Theorem 4.18](#) it suffices to work with \mathfrak{E}_ℓ . By [Theorem 4.19](#), $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell \in M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) \otimes S$. Its constant term at P_∞ is zero, because the cusp- ∞ analysis in the proof of [Theorem 4.19](#) shows $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell \in q\mathbf{Z}_p[[q]] \otimes S$. By [Theorem 4.26](#), $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell = aC_0 + buC_0$ with $a, b \in S$. The constant term at P_∞ gives $a = 0$, since $[q^0]C_0 = 1$ and $[q^0](uC_0) = 0$. Hence $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell \in S \cdot uC_0$, and [Theorem 4.18](#) gives the stated congruence for $g\Lambda_p(C_0\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell)$. \square

Lemma 4.28 (Parallel closure for uC_0). *For every split prime $p \geq 7$ and every $\ell = 1, 2, 3$,*

$$g\Lambda_p(uC_0\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell) \in (\mathbf{Z}_p/p^{4-\ell}\mathbf{Z}_p)C_0 \oplus (\mathbf{Z}_p/p^{4-\ell}\mathbf{Z}_p)uC_0.$$

Proof. Set $S = R/p^{4-\ell}R$, and let \mathfrak{E}'_ℓ be the analogue of (7) with uC_0 replacing C_0 . By [Theorem 4.19](#) applied with $f = uC_0$, $g\mathfrak{E}'_\ell \in M_5(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3) \otimes S$. Therefore [Theorem 4.26](#) gives $g\mathfrak{E}'_\ell \in SC_0 \oplus SuC_0$. The Cartier–Hecke comparison [Theorem 4.18](#) extends with uC_0 in place of C_0 , giving the asserted membership for $g\Lambda_p(uC_0\phi_p^\ell/p^\ell)$. \square

4.5. **Bridge scalar via Atkin–Lehner.** By [Theorems 4.27](#) and [4.28](#) together with the triangular conversion [Theorem 3.6](#), there are scalars $\alpha_\ell, \beta_\ell, \gamma_\ell \in \mathbf{Z}_p$ modulo $p^{4-\ell}$ such that

$$(8) \quad g\Lambda_p(C_0U_p^\ell) \equiv p^\ell \gamma_\ell uC_0 \pmod{p^4},$$

$$(9) \quad g\Lambda_p(uC_0U_p^\ell) \equiv p^\ell \alpha_\ell C_0 + p^\ell \beta_\ell uC_0 \pmod{p^4}.$$

The constant term at ∞ of the left side of (9) is zero, so $\alpha_\ell \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$.

Lemma 4.29 (Weakly holomorphic Atkin–Lehner intertwining). *Let $M_5^1(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$ denote the space of weight-5, χ_3 forms which are meromorphic only at the cusps. The Fricke pullback w_3^* preserves this space, and for every prime $p \nmid 3$,*

$$T_p w_3^* = \chi_3(p) w_3^* T_p$$

on $M_5^1(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$. With the geometric normalization used here, $w_3^* C_0 = -27uC_0$ and $w_3^*(uC_0) = -C_0/27$, and t is w_3 -invariant. Hence at split primes $\chi_3(p) = 1$,

$$(10) \quad \mathfrak{E}'_\ell = -\frac{1}{27} w_3^* \mathfrak{E}_\ell, \quad \ell = 1, 2, 3.$$

Proof. The operators w_3^* and T_p are defined by slash operators attached to matrices in $\mathrm{GL}_2^+(\mathbf{Q})$. These slash operators act on meromorphic modular forms just as on holomorphic modular forms; finite cusp principal parts remain finite cusp principal parts because the relevant maps are finite on the compact modular curve. Thus both operators preserve $M_5^1(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$. The identity $T_p w_3^* = \chi_3(p) w_3^* T_p$ is the original Atkin–Lehner double-coset identity [[2](#), §5, equation (58) and [Theorem 3](#)], established by computing the product of double cosets $\Gamma_0(3) \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \Gamma_0(3)$ and $\Gamma_0(3) \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix} \Gamma_0(3)$ in the Hecke algebra. The proof is an equality of finite sums of slash operators attached to double cosets, derived in a Hecke algebra independent of vanishing or holomorphy at the cusps; only the transformation law and the finite-dimensionality of cusp principal parts are used. The same calculation thus holds on the weakly holomorphic space $M_5^1(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$ as on the holomorphic subspace; for the explicit weakly-holomorphic extension of the Hecke formalism see [[7](#), §2].

The Fricke action on u is $w_3^* u = 1/(729u)$, and therefore

$$w_3^* t = \frac{w_3^* u}{(1 + 27w_3^* u)^2} = \frac{1/(729u)}{(1 + 1/(27u))^2} = \frac{u}{(1 + 27u)^2} = t.$$

The eta transformation $\eta(-1/\tau) = (-i\tau)^{1/2} \eta(\tau)$ with the geometric Fricke normalization gives $w_3^* C_0 = -27q + O(q^2)$ at the cusp ∞ , and $\mathrm{ord}_\infty(w_3^* C_0) = \mathrm{ord}_0(C_0) = 1$. Hence $w_3^* C_0$ has zero constant term. By [Theorem 4.26](#) over $R = \mathbf{Z}_p$, the holomorphic weight-5, χ_3 form $w_3^* C_0$ is an R -linear combination of C_0 and uC_0 ; the zero constant term kills the C_0 component, and the q^1 coefficient gives the scalar -27 . Thus $w_3^* C_0 = -27uC_0$. Applying $w_3^2 = \mathrm{id}$ gives $w_3^*(uC_0) = -C_0/27$.

We apply the weakly-holomorphic Atkin–Lehner intertwining only to the individual terms $T_p(C_0/t^{jp})$ and $T_p(uC_0/t^{jp})$, which are weakly holomorphic with finite cusp principal parts. The finite-difference combination $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ may have a pole at P_- before g -multiplication; the intertwining is not applied to $\mathfrak{E}_\ell(f)$ as an independent weakly holomorphic input.

Finally, apply w_3^* termwise to the finite difference defining $\mathfrak{E}_\ell = \mathfrak{E}_\ell(C_0)$. Since t is w_3 -invariant and $\chi_3(p) = 1$ for split primes,

$$\begin{aligned} w_3^* \mathfrak{E}_\ell &= \frac{1}{p^\ell} \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j w_3^* T_p \left(\frac{C_0}{t^{jp}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{p^\ell} \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j T_p w_3^* \left(\frac{C_0}{t^{jp}} \right) \\ &= -27 \frac{1}{p^\ell} \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} t^j T_p \left(\frac{uC_0}{t^{jp}} \right) = -27 \mathfrak{E}'_\ell. \end{aligned}$$

This is the asserted relation. \square

Remark 4.30 (Split-prime trivialization of the twist). The split-prime hypothesis $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ enters the Cartier–Hecke chain in two distinct places: (i) as the input condition for the μ_3 -equivariant canonical Frobenius normal form in [Theorem 4.5](#), and (ii) as the condition $\chi_3(p) = 1$ that makes the Atkin–Lehner intertwining $T_p w_3^* = \chi_3(p) w_3^* T_p$ untwisted. The bridge identity in [Theorem 4.31](#) relies specifically on the second trivialization. At inert primes $\chi_3(p) = -1$ would sign-flip the intertwining and break the bridge cancellation; this matches the q -side obstruction in [Section 5](#).

Corollary 4.31 (Bridge scalar cancellation). *For every split $p \geq 7$ and every $\ell = 1, 2, 3$,*

$$\beta_\ell \equiv 27^{-1} \gamma_\ell \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}, \quad \text{equivalently} \quad \gamma_\ell - 27\beta_\ell \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

Proof. By [Theorems 4.27](#) and [4.28](#) there are scalars $\Gamma_\ell, B_\ell \in \mathbf{Z}_p/p^{4-\ell}\mathbf{Z}_p$ with $g\mathfrak{E}_\ell \equiv \Gamma_\ell uC_0$ and $g\mathfrak{E}'_\ell \equiv B_\ell uC_0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$ (the C_0 -coefficient on the second side vanishes from constant-term considerations). The division by g below is performed in the common meromorphic lattice with possible pole at P_- , since g has a zero of order 1 on the coarse curve there. After multiplying back by g , the resulting congruence lies in the holomorphic M_5 -lattice modulo $p^{4-\ell}$. Using $w_3^*g = g/(27u)$, $w_3^*(uC_0) = -C_0/27$:

$$w_3^* \mathfrak{E}_\ell \equiv \Gamma_\ell \frac{w_3^*(uC_0)}{w_3^*g} = \Gamma_\ell \frac{-C_0/27}{g/(27u)} = -\Gamma_\ell \frac{uC_0}{g} \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}.$$

Combining with [\(10\)](#) and multiplying by g yields $g\mathfrak{E}'_\ell \equiv \Gamma_\ell/27 \cdot uC_0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$, so $B_\ell \equiv 27^{-1}\Gamma_\ell$. Since the scalar 27^{-1} is common to all three ϕ_p -layers, [Theorem 3.6](#) transfers the vector proportionality $B_\bullet \equiv 27^{-1}\Gamma_\bullet$ to the U_p -layer scalars, giving $\beta_\ell \equiv 27^{-1}\gamma_\ell$. \square

4.6. Mixed Cartier cancellation, transport, and the main theorem. The main result of this paper, [Theorem 4.33](#), depends only on [Theorem 4.32](#) below, the Katz–Dwork reduction [Theorem 3.8](#), and the Lagrange–Bürmann identity [Theorem 2.5](#). The companion Dwork congruence [[15](#), Thm. 7.8] for the diagonal point $(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}; 1)$ is used only in the optional [Theorem 4.34](#) (transport comparison with the base-side layers $C_0V_p^\ell$) and is not invoked anywhere in the proof of the main theorem.

Proposition 4.32 (Mixed Cartier cancellation). *For every split prime $p \geq 7$ and every $\ell = 1, 2, 3$,*

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}.$$

Proof. Apply Λ_p to $C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell = C_0U_p^\ell - 27uC_0U_p^\ell$ and multiply by g . Using [\(8\)](#), [\(9\)](#), and $\alpha_\ell \equiv 0$,

$$g\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv p^\ell(\gamma_\ell - 27\beta_\ell)uC_0 \pmod{p^4}.$$

By [Theorem 4.31](#), $\gamma_\ell - 27\beta_\ell \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$, hence $p^\ell(\gamma_\ell - 27\beta_\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$, so $g\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$. Since $g = 1 + O(q)$ is a unit in $\mathbf{Z}_p[[q]]$,

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}. \quad \square$$

Theorem 4.33 (Split-prime supercongruence). *For every split prime $p \geq 7$, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and every $m \geq 1$,*

$$A_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}.$$

Proof. By [Theorem 4.32](#), $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$. [Theorem 3.8](#) then gives, for every $m \geq 1$, the scalar Katz–Dwork congruence

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^{pm}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m \pmod{p^4}.$$

Extracting the coefficient of q^m and applying Lagrange–Bürmann ([Theorem 2.5](#)) gives $A_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$. \square

Theorem 4.34 (Conditional transport comparison). *Assume the truncated Dwork congruence at $(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}; 1)$ from [\[15, Thm. 7.8\]](#). For every split prime $p \geq 7$, every $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, and every $n \geq 1$,*

$$[q^{np}]C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell \equiv [q^{np}]C_0V_p^\ell \pmod{p^4}.$$

Proof. [Theorem 4.32](#) gives $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$. The companion theorem gives $\Lambda_p(C_0H_0^{pX}) \equiv C_0H_0^X \pmod{(p^4, X^4)}$, equivalent to $\Lambda_p(C_0V_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$. Subtracting,

$$\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell - C_0V_p^\ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4},$$

and the q^n -coefficient is exactly $[q^{np}](C_{\text{mix}}U_p^\ell - C_0V_p^\ell)$. \square

Remark 4.35 (Status of external inputs). We summarize the dependencies of [Section 4](#). The μ_3 -equivariance of the Frobenius lift at P_- follows from functoriality of Katz’s canonical subgroup under the $j = 0$ stabilizer ([Theorems 4.4 and 4.5](#)); the descended Katz trace operator is constructed internally on the ordinary locus, and its q -expansion at the cusp ∞ and at the cusp 0 is computed explicitly ([Theorems 4.9 and 4.21](#)); the coefficient extraction at P_- uses the trace-residue formula recorded in [Theorem 4.11](#); cusp-0 regularity of ϕ_p and of the two Eisenstein lines $C_0\psi^\ell$, $uC_0\psi^\ell$ is checked directly on the Fricke–Tate chart ([Theorems 4.20 and 4.22](#)); the local versus global Cartier–Hecke comparison is separated explicitly ([Theorems 4.18 and 4.19](#)); the weakly holomorphic Atkin–Lehner application is reduced to a double-coset identity acting on finite cusp principal parts ([Theorem 4.29](#)); the unit leading coefficient at P_- is proved from the theta representation and the local unit computation ([Theorems 4.1 and 4.2](#)); and mod p^N classicality is established directly through the coarse curve \mathbb{P}_u^1 together with the quotient-stack chart at P_- , without invoking any cohomological base-change theorem ([Theorems 4.25 and 4.26](#)). The divided finite differences are made integral by the elementary stacky weak q -expansion saturation at the non-stacky cusp P_∞ ([Theorems 4.16 and 4.17](#)); this uses only integrality of the special fibre and does not invoke Katz’s canonical q -expansion principle or any external mod- p^N machinery. The remaining external inputs are: Katz’s construction and functoriality of the canonical subgroup and ordinary normalized trace [[9, §§3.10–3.11](#)]; the tame quotient-stack local form at P_- [[1, Theorem 3.2](#)]; the trace-residue formula for finite flat extensions of complete one-dimensional local rings [[17, §3](#)], [[8, Ch. III](#)]; the Atkin–Lehner–Hecke double-coset identity [[2](#)]; and the Hecke theory of weakly holomorphic modular forms with finite cusp principal parts [[7](#)].

5. INERT-PRIME OBSTRUCTION

Define $C_{\text{mix}}(q) = 1 + \sum_{n \geq 1} c_n^{\text{mix}} q^n$. Set

$$s(n) := \sum_{d|n} \chi_3(d) d^4, \quad \beta(n) := \sum_{d|n} \chi_3(n/d) d^4.$$

Then $c_n^{\text{mix}} = 3s(n) - 27\beta(n)$.

Theorem 5.1 (Split-prime Eisenstein tower). *If $p \geq 5$ and $\chi_3(p) = 1$, then for all $m, r \geq 1$, $c_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv c_{mp^{r-1}}^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^{4r}}$.*

Proof. Both $s = 1 * (\chi_3 \text{id}^4)$ and $\beta = \chi_3 * \text{id}^4$ are multiplicative. For $p \neq 3$,

$$s(p^N) = \sum_{j=0}^N \chi_3(p)^j p^{4j}, \quad \beta(p^N) = \sum_{j=0}^N \chi_3(p)^{N-j} p^{4j}.$$

At $\chi_3(p) = 1$ both equal $1 + p^4 + \dots + p^{4N}$. Writing $m = p^a m_0$ with $(m_0, p) = 1$, $s(mp^r) - s(mp^{r-1}) = p^{4(a+r)} s(m_0)$, and similarly for β , giving the claim. \square

Theorem 5.2 (Inert-prime q -side obstruction). *Let $p \geq 5$, $\chi_3(p) = -1$. Then $\beta(p) - \beta(1) = p^4 - 2 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, and more generally if $m = p^a m_0$ with $p \nmid m_0$ and $\beta(m_0) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$,*

$$v_p(c_{mp}^{\text{mix}} - c_m^{\text{mix}}) = 0.$$

The obstruction comes from $\sum_N \beta(p^N) X^N = 1 / ((1 - \chi_3(p)X)(1 - p^4 X))$, whose unit-root factor is $(1 + X)^{-1}$ at inert primes.

Proof. For $\chi_3(p) = -1$, $\beta(1) = 1$ and $\beta(p) = -1 + p^4$, so $\beta(p) - \beta(1) = p^4 - 2$. For general $m = p^a m_0$,

$$\beta(mp) - \beta(m) = (\beta(p^{a+1}) - \beta(p^a))\beta(m_0).$$

Modulo p , $\beta(p^N) \equiv (-1)^N$, so the parenthesis is $-2(-1)^a \pmod{p}$, a unit. The s -part has valuation ≥ 4 , so the mixed coefficient difference has valuation 0 whenever $\beta(m_0)$ is a unit. \square

Proposition 5.3 (No split-style formal q -congruence at inert primes). *If $p \geq 5$ is inert, then $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}} H_{\text{mix}}^{pX}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}} H_{\text{mix}}^X \pmod{(p^4, X^4)}$ cannot hold.*

Proof. Set $X = 0$: the congruence implies $c_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv c_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$ for every $m \geq 1$, contradicting [Theorem 5.2](#). \square

For the coefficient-level statement, it is useful to keep both Eisenstein branches visible. For $\varepsilon \in \{\pm 1\}$, define

$$C^{(\varepsilon)}(q) := C_0(q) - 27\varepsilon u(q)C_0(q), \quad A_m^{(\varepsilon)} := [q^m]C^{(\varepsilon)}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q)^m.$$

Thus $A_m^{(+1)} = A_m^{\text{mix}}$, while $A_m^{(-1)}$ is the conjugate Eisenstein branch obtained by changing the sign of the second Eisenstein component.

Theorem 5.4 (Inert Cartier parity on the coefficient sequence). *For every prime $p \geq 5$, every $r \geq 0$, and every $m \geq 0$,*

$$A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{(\chi_3(p)^r)} \pmod{p}.$$

Consequently, if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then

$$A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p},$$

whereas if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then

$$A_{mp^{2r}}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p}, \quad A_{mp^{2r+1}}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{(-1)} \pmod{p}.$$

Proof. Write Λ_p^r for the r -fold Cartier operator. By [Theorem 2.5](#),

$$A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} = [q^{mp^r}]C_{\text{mix}}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{mp^r}.$$

Since $H_{\text{mix}} \in 1 + q\mathbf{Z}[[q]]$, the freshman Frobenius congruence gives

$$H_{\text{mix}}(q)^{mp^r} \equiv H_{\text{mix}}(q^{p^r})^m \pmod{p}.$$

Therefore

$$A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv [q^{mp^r}]C_{\text{mix}}(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q^{p^r})^m = [q^m]\Lambda_p^r(C_{\text{mix}})(q)H_{\text{mix}}(q)^m \pmod{p}.$$

It remains to compute $\Lambda_p^r(C_{\text{mix}})$ modulo p . The constant term is preserved on C_0 and is zero on uC_0 . For positive coefficients, write $n = p^a n_0$ with $p \nmid n_0$, and set $\chi = \chi_3(p)$. From

$$s(p^N) = \sum_{j=0}^N \chi^j p^{4j}, \quad \beta(p^N) = \sum_{j=0}^N \chi^{N-j} p^{4j},$$

we get

$$s(p^{a+r} n_0) \equiv s(p^a n_0) \pmod{p}, \quad \beta(p^{a+r} n_0) \equiv \chi^r \beta(p^a n_0) \pmod{p}.$$

Hence

$$\Lambda_p^r(C_0) \equiv C_0 \pmod{p}, \quad \Lambda_p^r(uC_0) \equiv \chi_3(p)^r uC_0 \pmod{p},$$

and so

$$\Lambda_p^r(C_{\text{mix}}) \equiv C_0 - 27\chi_3(p)^r uC_0 = C^{(\chi_3(p)^r)} \pmod{p}.$$

Substitution gives the asserted congruence. \square

Corollary 5.5 (One-step inert failure on the coefficient sequence). *For every inert prime $p \geq 5$,*

$$A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv 72 \pmod{p}.$$

In particular, since $A_1^{\text{mix}} = 18$,

$$A_p^{\text{mix}} - A_1^{\text{mix}} \equiv 54 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p},$$

so the split-style congruence $A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_1^{\text{mix}}$ fails already modulo p .

Proof. By [Theorem 5.4](#), $A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_1^{(-1)} \pmod{p}$. Since $uC_0 = q + O(q^2)$ and $H_{\text{mix}} = 1 + O(q)$, one has $[q]uC_0 H_{\text{mix}} = 1$. Thus

$$A_1^{(-1)} - A_1^{(+1)} = 54[q]uC_0 H_{\text{mix}} = 54.$$

The sequence begins with $A_1^{\text{mix}} = 18$, hence $A_1^{(-1)} = 72$. Since $p \geq 5$ and $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, $p \nmid 54$. \square

Remark 5.6. The split condition $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ is essential twice: in [Section 4](#) it gives the μ_3 -equivariant canonical Frobenius lift at P_- , while here $\chi_3(p) = -1$ produces the unit-root obstruction in the second Eisenstein factor.

6. COMPUTATIONAL VERIFICATION

All computations used exact rational arithmetic followed by reduction modulo p^k , with q -precision $N = 5p^2$. Implementation in SageMath; coefficient extraction for Λ_p and the Hecke finite difference performed independently.

- (1) *Closure consequence at split primes.* The local pole estimate [Theorem 4.13](#) is not tested directly through the unknown local coefficients α_i . Instead, we verify the global consequences

$$\frac{g\Lambda_p(C_0 U_p^\ell)}{p^\ell} \equiv \gamma_\ell uC_0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}, \quad \frac{g\Lambda_p(uC_0 U_p^\ell)}{p^\ell} \equiv \beta_\ell uC_0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}},$$

for $p \in \{7, 13, 19, 31\}$ and $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. All 24 residuals vanish identically through q^{5p} after Cartier extraction. For $p = 7$ the bridge scalars are $(\gamma_1, \beta_1) = (95, 283)$, $(\gamma_2, \beta_2) = (36, 34)$, $(\gamma_3, \beta_3) = (6, 1)$; for $p = 13$, $(\gamma_1, \beta_1) = (363, 1234)$, $(\gamma_2, \beta_2) = (33, 20)$, $(\gamma_3, \beta_3) = (4, 4)$. In every case $\gamma_\ell - 27\beta_\ell \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$. The Cartier–Hecke comparison [Theorem 4.18](#) is verified independently by computing \mathfrak{E}_ℓ directly.

- (2) *Bridge scalar.* The cancellation $\gamma_\ell - 27\beta_\ell \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{4-\ell}}$ from [Theorem 4.31](#) was checked directly at $p = 7$ for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$.
- (3) *Layer divisibility.* $\phi_p \in pq\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$ verified coefficient-wise through q^{5p^2} for $p \in \{7, 13, 19, 31\}$.
- (4) *Hecke numerator saturation.* For $f \in \{C_0, uC_0\}$, $p \in \{7, 13\}$, and $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, the numerator $N_\ell(f)$ of [Theorem 4.17](#) was checked to satisfy $q_\infty(N_\ell(f)) \in p^\ell \mathbf{Z}_p((q))$, with exact minimum valuation ℓ in every tested case.

- (5) *Scalar Katz–Dwork congruence.* The scalar congruence $\Lambda_p(C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^{pm}) \equiv C_{\text{mix}}H_{\text{mix}}^m \pmod{p^4}$ was checked through the equivalent truncated X -expansion for $p \in \{7, 13, 19, 31\}$ to precision $5p^2$.
- (6) *Inert branch-swap.* $p \in \{5, 11\}$: the Eisenstein coefficient tower fails with valuation 0, as predicted by [Theorem 5.2](#). The tested A -level samples agree with the theorem-level Cartier parity law of [Theorem 5.4](#); in particular $A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv 72 \pmod{p}$ and $A_p^{\text{mix}} - 18$ has valuation 0, as predicted by [Theorem 5.5](#).
- (7) *MUM signature.* $A_{p-1}^{\text{mix}} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ holds for all tested split p with $7 \leq p \leq 97$ and fails at all tested inert p with $5 \leq p \leq 83$.

CONCLUSION

The split-prime p^4 supercongruence

$$A_{mp}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$$

at the mixed CM point $(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{3}; 1)$ is proved unconditionally for every split prime $p \geq 7$, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and every $m \geq 1$. The matching inert-prime behavior is also theorem-level. On the q -side, the Eisenstein coefficient tower rules out the split-style formal parameter congruence at inert primes. On the coefficient sequence itself, [Theorem 5.4](#) proves the exact first-digit branch law

$$A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{(\chi_3(p)^r)} \pmod{p},$$

so for inert primes one Frobenius step exchanges the two Eisenstein branches and two steps return to the original branch. In particular $A_p^{\text{mix}} \equiv 72 \pmod{p}$ for every inert $p \geq 5$, and $A_p^{\text{mix}} \not\equiv A_1^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p}$. The local mechanism producing the extra digit beyond the Roberts–Rodriguez Villegas weight-3 prediction is the μ_3 -equivariant length-three Witt–Cartier pole estimate at the tame elliptic stack point $j = 0$. Natural next questions are the higher-precision split tower $A_{mp^r}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_{mp^{r-1}}^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^{4r}}$ for $r \geq 2$, the inert Frobenius-square strengthening $A_{mp^2}^{\text{mix}} \equiv A_m^{\text{mix}} \pmod{p^4}$, and the third order-drop CM point $(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{6}; 1)$ with $\lambda = 432$.

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